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D1.3 ECO-DESIGN AND DESIGN FOR RECYCLABILITY GUIDELINES

30/11/2025

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This work has received funding from the Swiss State Secretariat for Education, Research and Innovation (SERI)

PROJECT GENERAL INFORMATION

Project Acronym	SOLVE
Project Title	Advancing SOLid-state battery development and production to driVE the future of electromobility
Grant Agreement Number	101147094
Call	HORIZON-CL5-2023-D2-02-01
Project Coordinator	Fundación CIDETEC
Project Duration	01 June 2024 – 31 May 2028 (48 months)

DELIVERABLE GENERAL INFORMATION

Deliverable No.	D1.3 Eco-design and design for recyclability guidelines
Dissemination level*	PUB
Work Package	WP1 – Specifications, life cycle assessments and regulatory compliance
Tasks	T1.4 – Eco-design guidelines T1.5 – SSB design for recyclability
Lead beneficiary	LOM
Contributing beneficiary	ACC
Reviewers	Dane Sotta (CEA) Elisabetta Fedeli (SAFT)
Date of deliverable	30 November 2025

DOCUMENT HISTORY

v	Date	Summary of Main Changes
1.0	17/10/2025	First draft of the deliverable
1.1	01/11/2025	Updated version with comments and modifications (Andriy Kvasha, CID)
2.0	12/11/2025	Updated version after incorporation of feedback from CID
2.1	21/11/2025	Updated version with comments and modifications (Elisabetta Fedeli, SAFT)
2.2	24/11/2025	Updated version with comments and modifications (Dane Sotta, CEA)
3.0	25/11/2025	Update version after incorporation of feedback from SAFT and CEA
4.0	27/11/2025	Final version

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LIST OF ABBREVIATIONS

Acronym	Meaning
AF	Anode-free
BoM	Bill of Materials
BP	Battery Passport
CAM	Cathode Active Material
CRM	Critical Raw Material
DOD	Depth of Discharge
DPP	Digital Product Passport
EC	European Commission
EF	Environmental footprint
EHS	Environmental, health, and safety
EoL	End-of-Life
EPR	Extended Producer Responsibility
ESPR	Eco-design for Sustainable Products Regulation
EU	European Union
EV	Electric Vehicle
FU	Functional unit
HSPE	Hybrid solid polymer-based electrolyte
LCA	Life Cycle Assessment
LCI	Life Cycle Inventory
LCIA	Life Cycle Impact Assessment
LIB	Lithium-ion battery

LiM	Lithium metal
LMT	Light Means of Transport
LREE	Light Rare Earth Elements
NFPA	National Fire Protection Association
NMC	Layered Mixed Transition Metal Oxide, $\text{LiNi}_x\text{Mn}_y\text{Co}_z\text{O}_2$ ($x+y+z=1$)
PLD	Pulsed Laser Deposition
RMIS	Raw Materials Information System
SRM	Strategic Raw Material
SSB	Solid-state battery
SSbD	Safe and Sustainable by Design
VGCF	Vapor Grown Carbon Fiber
WP	Work Package

EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

The SOLVE project aims to accelerate the development and production of next-generation solid-state batteries (SSBs) to drive the future of electromobility. Its core objective is to design, validate, and demonstrate sustainable and high-performance battery systems capable of meeting the demanding requirements of both automotive and aviation applications. To achieve this, SOLVE focuses on two complementary cell architectures: the **Lithium Metal Solid-State Battery (LiM-SSB)** and the **Anode-Free Solid-State Battery (AF-SSB)**.

The LiM-SSB configuration integrates an ultra-thin lithium metal anode, targeting high energy density and improved safety through the use of hybrid solid polymer electrolytes (HSPEs). Meanwhile, the AF-SSB design eliminates excess lithium at the anode side, instead employing lithiophilic current collectors and innovative barrier layers to further enhance sustainability and resource efficiency. Together, these architectures aim to demonstrate the technological and environmental feasibility of solid-state batteries in line with the EU's strategic objectives for clean energy transition and resource independence.

To this end, Deliverable, **D1.3, titled "Eco-design and design for recyclability guidelines"** encompasses the activities carried out in **Task 1.4 – "Ecodesign guidelines"**, led by LOMARTOV; and **Task 1.5 – "SSB design for recyclability"**, led by ACCUREC. The core objective of this work is to proactively integrate sustainability considerations into the early design stages of novel SSB chemistries and components, ensuring that development is aligned with and anticipates the evolving European regulatory framework, including the landmark EU Battery Regulation (EU 2023/1542), the Eco-design for Sustainable Products Regulation (ESPR) (EU 2024/1781), and the EU Critical Raw Materials (CRM) Act (EU 2024/1252).

To achieve this goal, the deliverable employed a hybrid methodological approach. First, a streamlined **Life Cycle Assessment (LCA)** was conducted, adhering to the ISO 14040/44 framework. Given the early stage of the project, the system boundary was intentionally limited to a **cradle-to-gate perspective**, meaning that only the impacts from raw material extraction, precursor production, and synthesis up to the point where the materials leave the manufacturing facility were considered. In other words, use-phase and End-of-Life (EoL) stages were excluded at this point. This boundary choice enabled a timely and consistent comparison of material alternatives at a moment when design decisions are still flexible and can most effectively influence sustainability outcomes.

Second, a **Safe and Sustainable by Design (SSbD)** scorecard was developed, which is a consolidated scoring system with the goal of holistically evaluating the sustainability profile of materials proposed for the high-loading solid-state cathode, the hybrid solid polymer-based electrolyte (HSPE), and lithium metal (LiM) anode barrier layers. This scorecard synthesised critical performance data across four equally weighted indicators: hazard level, CRM content (criticality), cost, and the LCA single score.

The application of the SSbD scorecard yielded targeted eco-design recommendations across all assessed components. Although they are not competing alternatives NMC 85:5:10 CAM powder ($LiNi_{0.85}Mn_{0.05}Co_{0.1}O_2$ for LiM-SSB) presented a slightly better sustainable profile than Li-rich NMC ($Li_{1.2}Ni_{0.1}Mn_{0.6}Co_{0.1}O_2$ for AF-SSB), especially due to the lower criticality and cost of the former. Among cathode coatings, lithium zirconate (Li_2ZrO_3) emerged as the most sustainable material, demonstrating the lowest criticality (0.05) and lowest LCA single score (0.28), while lithium borate (Li_3BO_3) was identified as the least favourable option due to high scores in all four categories. For conductive additives, carbon black was preferred over vapor growth carbon fibres (VGCF), whose energy-intensive production process resulted in environmental impacts dominated by electricity consumption. LiBOB stood out among lithium salts for its very low cost and criticality, and the plasticiser PYR14FSI was favoured over PYR14TFSI due to the TFSI anion's higher environmental footprint and cost. Crucially, the analysis of HSPE ceramic fillers showed that modifying LAMP to Si@LAMP incurred a significant environmental penalty due to the added solvents and reagents, making the unmodified LAMP a substantially more favourable option. Finally, the most sustainable LiM anode barrier layer was determined to be LLZO (lithium lanthanum zirconium oxide), which consistently performed best across all four SSbD indicators, whereas lithium nitride (Li_3N) proved the least sustainable.

This systematic assessment provides a crucial foundation for developers to select materials that mitigate environmental, health, and supply chain risks in the pursuit of high-performance SSBs.

With respect to the recyclability evaluation (Task 1.5), it is essential to align the SSB development with the stringent EoL management requirements of the EU Battery Regulation (EU 2023/1542). This analysis identified crucial safety and environmental hazards inherent in novel chemistry: specifically, the use of lithium metal as the anode material, and the incorporation of highly fluorinated organic compounds (PFAS) in inactive materials, such as polymers, lithium salts (e.g., LiTFSI, LiFSI), and plasticisers. The presence of LiM demands strict avoidance of water contact during pre-treatment, while the fluorinated organics complicate subsequent recycling steps by remaining in recovered fractions as impurities. To mitigate these risks and ensure the compliance required to meet ambitious material recovery targets (e.g., 90% for Ni, Co, and Cu by 2027), the thermal de-activation route was pre-selected as the optimal pre-treatment strategy. Thermal processing effectively de-activates the lithium metal by converting it into soluble salts, while simultaneously degrading the fluorinated compounds and polymer matrix. This approach increases the overall recovery rate and purity by releasing the CAM. This tailored recycling strategy is expected to yield a clean input material (black mass) suitable for subsequent hydrometallurgical processing, facilitating the efficient recovery of critical raw materials like Nickel (Ni), Cobalt (Co), and Manganese (Mn).

1. INTRODUCTION

1.1. OBJECTIVES OF THE WORK

The main objective of this deliverable is to establish a comprehensive framework for the eco-design and design for recyclability of the solid-state battery (SSB) technologies developed within the SOLVE project. Building upon the objectives of **Task 1.4 – Eco-design guidelines** and **Task 1.5 – SSB design for recyclability**, this work integrates the principles of **Safe and Sustainable by Design (SSbD)** to ensure that materials, components, and processes developed across the project achieve an optimal balance between **performance, sustainability, and circularity**.

The work conducted under **Task 1.4** focuses on the systematic evaluation of environmental impacts associated with the materials and manufacturing processes of the two SOLVE cell configurations – LiM-SSB and AF-SSB. This involves the use of **streamlined life cycle assessment** and the development of a **material scorecards** that combine environmental, safety, economic, and criticality indicators. These tools serve to identify environmental hotspots, guide material substitution, and promote resource efficiency from a **cradle-to-cradle perspective**. Through this approach, eco-design principles are embedded into the early stages of technology development, enabling informed decision-making for materials selection and process optimization.

Complementarily, **Task 1.5 (Design for recyclability)** ensures that sustainability considerations extend beyond the use phase by addressing **End-of-Life (EoL) management** and recyclability aspects in alignment with the **EU Battery Regulation (2023/1542)**. The assessment focuses on the recoverability of key components (electrodes, electrolyte, foils, and casings) and evaluates potential recycling routes to maximize material recovery and minimize waste generation. These insights directly support the identification of design features that facilitate future disassembly and recycling of SOLVE cells.

Together, the outcomes of Tasks 1.4 and 1.5 converge in this deliverable (D1.3), which provides actionable **eco-design and recyclability guidelines** for developers and manufacturers. The overarching goal is to ensure that the next generation of SOLVE solid-state batteries combines **technical excellence with environmental responsibility**, fostering the transition toward a sustainable and circular European battery value chain.

1.2. REGULATORY FRAMEWORK SUPPORTING THE WORK OBJECTIVES

1.2.1. EU 2023/1542 BATTERY REGULATION

The EU released in **August 2023** the **Battery Regulation** (EU 2023/1542), which replaced the EU Battery Directive (2006/66 EC) [1]. It represents a milestone in European policy for sustainable energy storage, being part of the EU Green Deal and complementing both the Circular Economy and Strategic Action Plans on batteries, as illustrated in **Figure 1**.

Figure 1: Effect of the main European policy initiatives on the formulation of the Battery Regulation.

Unlike its predecessor, this regulation sets the ground for a directly applicable legal framework which covers the entire battery value chain, from raw material extraction to End-of-Life (EoL) management. The main purposes of the Battery Regulation are listed as follows [1]:

- Promoting sustainability in the production stage, as well as reducing the environmental impacts caused during the battery's life cycle.
- Ensuring safety through the human health and environmental protection.
- Encouraging circularity by making data available to enable second life usage.
- Improving transparency and consumer information in terms of safety and environmental performance of the batteries.

In addition, the Battery Regulation also:

- Covers the entire life cycle of the batteries (circular economy).
- Ensures proper collection and recycling of waste batteries.
- Reduces environmental and social impacts of batteries.
- Applies to all type of batteries.

Strict requirements are set for different battery categories, including portable batteries, industrial batteries, electric vehicle (EV) batteries and batteries for light means of transport (LMT). It introduces mandatory due diligence rules for sourcing of raw materials, minimum levels of recycled content (e.g., for Co, Pb, Li, and Ni), carbon footprint declarations, and extended producer responsibility (EPR) schemes.

With respect to the EPRs, they have been clearly reinforced. This is evidenced by the prior Battery Directive, which for the first time incorporates environmental activities (part of the so-called Environmental Framework Conditions in chapter 2) into the circular cycle of a battery (see **Figure 2**) [2].

Figure 2: The new EU regulatory framework for batteries [2].

Within this framework, the EC created the **battery passport (BP)**, the first digital product passport (DPP) introduced in Europe. The BP will be an electronic record of a battery containing a comprehensive set of information collected along the battery life cycle. It is expected to be adopted by February 2027 and will allow a more efficient recycling, as the availability of data on battery composition and dismantling will enhance the efficiency of recycling processes. Its main purposes will be to provide tracking and transparency of information to facilitate decision-making throughout the battery lifetime, especially in relation to its EoL.

Regarding the battery eco-design, the BP plays a crucial role in facilitating the implementation of design principles that promote sustainability and resource efficiency and contribute to a circular economy. By providing detailed data and labelling on battery composition and performance, the system enables designers to optimize battery design to maximize lifespan, enhance energy efficiency and facilitate EoL recycling.

Finally, in the context of **solid-state batteries (SSBs)**, the regulation is especially relevant regarding two aspects: **(i)** first, reporting on carbon footprint and environmental performance is mandatory for all EV batteries **above 2 kWh**, meaning that SSBs must comply with the same reporting and labelling requirements as conventional lithium-ion batteries (LIBs); **(ii)** second, the ambitious targets for recycling efficiency and material recovery create both a challenge and an opportunity, since current recycling routes for solid electrolytes and novel electrode compositions are not yet fully established. Therefore, the Battery Regulation provides both a regulatory driver and a framework for innovation, ensuring that SSBs are designed with EoL management in mind from the beginning.

1.2.2. ECO-DESIGN FOR SUSTAINABLE PRODUCTS REGULATION

The new **Eco-design for Sustainable Products Regulation (ESPR)** (EU 2024/1781) was adopted on **June 13, 2024** as part of the EC's Sustainable Products Initiative, under the umbrella of the Circular Economy Action Plan and the European Green Deal [3]. This regulation poses a step forward in the EU's ambition to promote environmentally sustainable and circular products. Unlike the previous Eco-design directive (2009/125/EC), which mainly covered energy-related products, the ESPR applies a much broader scope, extending to nearly all groups placed on the EU market, with a few exceptions such as food and feed.

The ESPR presents a comprehensive framework, aiming at enhancing the circularity, energy efficiency, and overall environmental sustainability of these products. Some of the key aspects covered by the proposed requirements include:

- *Improving product durability, reusability, upgradability, and repairability.*
- *Promoting the use of recycled content.*
- *Addressing the presence of substances that obstruct circularity.*
- *Assessing carbon and environmental footprints.*
- *Facilitating remanufacturing and recycling processes.*
- *Enhancing energy and resource efficiency.*

It is worth mentioning that this regulation redefines the concept of eco-design as the integration of sustainability considerations across the product value chain, rather than a single intervention at the design stage. For the case of **SSBs**, these provisions directly align with the objectives of the SOLVE project, since critical aspects such as durability, recyclability, avoidance of critical substances, and life cycle environmental impacts are explicitly addressed within the ESPR framework. This reinforces the relevance of applying eco-design premises early in the development process.

As eco-design is an approach that needs continuous intervention throughout the whole life cycle of a product, technology, or process; it is necessary to narrow the proposed eco-design strategies to meet the aim of their implementation. Within this context, **Table 1** provides a structured mapping between the general ESPR requirements and their practical implications for SSB development within the SOLVE project.

Table 1. Mapping of ESPR requirements to SSB and their practical implications within SOLVE.

ESPR eco-design requirement	Relevance for SSBs	Practical implications within SOLVE
Durability and reliability	Directly linked to cycle life, safety under long-term use, and mechanical integrity of the electrolyte	Development of battery modules that maintain performance over 500 (80% DOD) and 3000 (50% DOD) cycles without degradation
Ease of repair and maintenance	More important at module/pack level than at cell level (replacement of defective units)	Design modular architectures where defective SSB modules can be replaced instead of scrapping entire packs
Ease of upgrading, re-use, remanufacturing and refurbishment	Potential for second-life use in stationary storage	Design cells that can be disassembled and re-assembled without compromising safety, allowing refurbishment
Ease and quality of recycling	Critical recovery for lithium, cobalt, manganese, nickel, and solid electrolytes	Use electrolyte and binder systems that are separable in EoL processing
Avoidance of technical solutions detrimental to recyclability	Composite architectures and ceramic-polymer hybrids can hinder recycling	Prioritize architectures with clearly separable components and compatible materials
Use of substances of concern	Avoiding hazardous solvents or dopants in electrolyte and binder production	Screen precursors regarding their intrinsic hazard and criticality; substitution of high-risk chemicals when possible; dry processing of HSPE
Energy use or energy efficiency	Mainly relevant during manufacturing stage	Optimize synthesis routes and evaluate energy usage hotspots in Life Cycle Assessment (LCA)
Resource use or resource efficiency	Concerns both critical raw materials and yield losses in processes	Design processing with minimal material waste; maximize utilization of precursors
Recycled content	Still emerging for SSBs, but relevant in module casing, current collectors, etc.	Use of recycled aluminium current collectors in the cathode; limited options for the anodic side elements
Weight and volume of product and packaging	SSB aim at offering higher energy densities compared to conventional ones, reducing overall pack size and materials per kWh	Optimize component thicknesses and stack design to balance energy density with safety and recyclability
Environmental footprint (LCA)	A cradle-to-cradle approach is necessary to benchmark SSBs against conventional LIBs	Use streamlined LCA in early development stages; refined with detailed inventory data in later stages

ESPR eco-design requirement	Relevance for SSBs	Practical implications within SOLVE
Carbon footprint	Strong emphasis in ESPR; SSB must demonstrate better or at least similar performance with respect to LIBs	Quantify CO ₂ emissions per kWh delivered and identify process improvements to reduce hotspots
Emissions and waste generations	Relevant to both solvent use in electrode processing and ceramic powder synthesis	Minimize solvent emissions, optimize waste management strategies, and enable closed-loop recycling of solvents
Conditions of use	Safety under critical conditions, such as thermal runaway or short circuits	Ensure non-flammable electrolytes and stable interphases to withstand high voltage and temperature

1.2.3. SAFE AND SUSTAINABLE BY DESIGN

The European Commission's recommended **Safe and Sustainable by Design (SSbD)** framework is an approach intended to evaluate the safety and sustainability of new materials during their innovation process, as well as re-assess these criteria for already-existing materials. The framework comprises two stages: **design stage**, and **safety and sustainability assessment stage** [4].

Its main goal is to provide a function or service and simultaneously avoid the use of large quantities of chemicals and materials that could pose risks to human health or to the environment, especially focusing on chemical groups prone to (eco)toxicity, persistence, bioaccumulation, or mobility. To this end, it is necessary to reduce the environmental impacts of chemicals and materials adopting a lifecycle perspective, particularly those concerning climate change, resource utilization, and safeguarding ecosystems and biodiversity [4].

Thus, the safety and sustainability assessment stage of the SSbD framework consists of four aspects, listed as follows:

- **Hazardous properties** of the chemical or material under consideration.
- **Human health and safety aspects** of its **production and processing**.
- **Hazards and risks** associated with its **final application**.
- **Environmental impacts** throughout its **life cycle**.

It should be clear that the SSbD framework focuses on assessing the safety and sustainability of chemicals and materials employed in products rather than products themselves. This emphasis makes it a valuable tool for generating eco-design recommendations, particularly regarding the selection of low-impact materials and minimizing material usage.

1.2.4. EU CRITICAL RAW MATERIALS ACT

Raw materials serve as the pillar of industrial production, technological innovation, and economic development. Nonetheless, their availability and accessibility are not always guaranteed. Recognizing the strategic importance and supply chain vulnerabilities associated with certain raw materials critical to its industrial base, the European Union adopted the **Critical Raw Materials (CRM) Act**. This Regulation (EU 2024/1252) was formally approved by the Council in March 2024 and entered into force on **May 23, 2024** [5].

The CRM Act establishes a comprehensive framework for ensuring a secure and sustainable supply of CRMs, providing an updated list alongside a designation of Strategic Raw Materials (SRM). The latter are crucial in technologies vital to Europe's green and digital ambitions, as well as for applications in defence and space; however, they are susceptible to potential future supply risks. The Regulation integrates both

the CRMs and SRMs into the EU law, providing a tool to address supply chain vulnerabilities and reinforce the continent's economic resilience.

In order to create this list, the EC's criticality methodology is implemented, where every raw material within the study is evaluated according to two criteria: their **economic importance (EI)** and their **supply risk (SR)** to the European market. A material's EI is calculated based on its importance for end-use applications and on the performance of available substitutes in those applications, while the SR is calculated according to factors that measure the risk of a disruption in the supply of the material. The thresholds for both criteria are $SR \geq 1.0$ and $EI \geq 2.8$, so a material exceeding both of them is considered critical [5].

SR and EI values for each raw material were sourced from the 2023 Critical Raw Materials Study – Final Report [6], as formally adopted in the EC's methodology. Although the explicit values are not embedded in the Regulation text itself, they support the material selection logic and thresholds. The list of all assessed raw materials in the 2023 criticality study along with their respective values of SR and EI can be found in **Table 2**.

Table 2. SR and EI values for all raw materials assessed in the 2023 criticality study [6].

Material	SR	EI	Material	SR	EI	Material	SR	EI
Aggregates	0.2	3.2	Hydrogen	0.5	2.9	Potash	0.7	6.2
Aluminium	1.1	5.5	Indium	0.6	2.6	Rhenium	0.5	2.3
Antimony	1.8	5.4	Iron ore	0.5	7.2	Roundwood	0.1	1.2
Arsenic	1.9	2.9	Kaolin clay	0.8	2.8	Sapele wood	1.3	1.6
Baryte	1.3	3.5	Krypton	0.7	3.3	Scandium	2.4	3.7
Bentonite	0.4	3.1	Lead	0.1	4.2	Selenium	0.3	4.8
Beryllium	1.8	5.4	Limestone	0.3	3.6	Silica sand	0.3	3.1
Bismuth	1.9	5.7	Lithium	1.9	3.9	Silicon metal	1.4	4.9
Boron	3.6	3.9	LREEs	3.7	5.9	Silver	0.8	4.6
Cadmium	0.2	4.1	Magnesite	0.6	3.6	Strontium	2.6	6.5
Chromium	0.7	7.2	Magnesium	4.1	7.4	Sulphur	0.3	5
Cobalt	2.8	6.8	Manganese	1.2	6.9	Talc	0.2	3.3
Coking coal	1	3.1	Molybdenum	0.8	6.7	Tantalum	1.3	4.8
Copper	0.1	4	Natural cork	0.9	1.7	Tellurium	0.3	3.8
Diatomite	0.3	2.3	Natural graphite	1.8	3.4	Tin	0.9	4.5

Material	SR	EI	Material	SR	EI	Material	SR	EI
Feldspar	1.5	3.2	Natural Rubber	0.9	6	Titanium	0.5	5.4
Fluorspar	1.1	3.8	Natural Teak wood	1.7	2.4	Titanium metal	1.6	6.3
Gallium	3.9	3.7	Neon	0.7	3.1	Tungsten	1.2	8.7
Germanium	1.8	3.6	Nickel	0.5	5.7	Vanadium	2.3	3.9
Gold	0.4	2.4	Niobium	4.4	6.5	Xenon	0.8	3.1
Gypsum	0.6	2.7	Perlite	0.8	2.5	Zinc	0.2	4.8
Hafnium	1.5	4.3	Pt group metals	2.7	7.1	Zirconium	0.8	3.5
Helium	1.2	2.9	Phosphate rock	1	6.4			
HREEs	5.1	4.2	Phosphorus	3.3	4.7			

Moreover, the 2024 CRMs list for the EU is presented in **Table 3**. Materials in **bold** are categorized as **Strategic Raw Materials (SRM)**, meaning that they are considered essential for technologies that promote the green and digital transition as well as the defence and aerospace goals. Materials shaded in **light blue** (i.e., copper and nickel) does not meet the SR threshold (0.1 and 0.5, respectively); however, they are considered as CRMs in the 2024/1252 Regulation.

Table 3. Critical Raw Materials list for the EU in 2024 [5].

2024 Critical Raw Materials Act

antimony	copper	lithium	scandium
arsenic	feldspar	magnesium	silicon metal
bauxite/alumina/aluminium	fluorspar	manganese	strontium
baryte	gallium	graphite	tantalum
beryllium	germanium	nickel – battery grade	titanium metal
bismuth	hafnium	niobium	tungsten
boron	helium	phosphate rock	vanadium
cobalt	heavy rare earths	phosphorus	
coking coal	light rare earths	Pt group metals	

2. METHODOLOGY

2.1. LIFE CYCLE ASSESSMENT

Life cycle assessment (LCA) has become a key tool for formal evaluation of the environmental performance of products and processes, and has been increasingly integrated into both public policy and private sector decision-making [7]. Nevertheless, the practical implementation of a full LCA often remains challenging, as it requires large amounts of detailed data, can be time- and resource-intensive, and is usually subject to high uncertainty, especially when considering upstream and downstream life cycle stages that fall outside the control of the technology developers.

To address these issues, several streamlining approaches have been developed, aiming at simplifying the procedure while retaining its decision-support value [8,9]. Screening LCAs, for instance, limit system boundaries or omit stages for which data are unavailable or expected to contribute marginally to the overall impacts. Although such approaches may sacrifice a detailed quantification of uncertainty, they can still deliver robust insights in contexts where early feedback is essential.

This is precisely the case in SOLVE, where the technologies under development – novel SSB chemistries and components – are still at laboratory or pilot scale, with limited availability of reliable data for downstream use and EoL phases. Here, the streamlined LCA provides timely indicators to guide material selection, outlining potential environmental trade-offs and ensuring that eco-design recommendations are implemented at early stage.

The streamlined LCA methodology applied in SOLVE is consistent with the **four stages** of the ISO 14040/44 framework:

- 1) *Goal and scope definition*
- 2) *Life Cycle Inventory analysis*
- 3) *Life Cycle Impact Assessment*
- 4) *Interpretation of results*

A **full cradle-to-grave assessment** of the two SOLVE cell concepts (LiM-SSB and AF-SSB) will be carried out in **D4.4 – SSB impact assessment** once the complete set of components has been selected, integrated, and tested at prototype level. That forthcoming analysis will provide an exhaustive picture of the environmental performance across all life cycle stages, from raw material extraction through manufacturing, use phase, and End-of-Life management, hence complementing the early-stage insights presented here.

However, in the context of this deliverable, the **scope** of the LCA has been intentionally reduced to a **cradle-to-gate** perspective, putting the boundaries at the extraction plus the manufacturing of the proposed materials. This streamlined approach ensures that sustainability considerations can be integrated at a point where they are most impactful, even if comprehensive data for later stages are not yet available (e.g., the use stage). The **allocation at point of substitution – unit (APOS, U)** system was applied, following an attributional approach in which the responsibility over wastes is shared between producers and subsequent users benefiting from the treatment processes by using valuable products generated in these.

With respect to the **functional unit (FU)**, it was defined as **1 kg of synthesised material**. This choice is particularly relevant when the focus lies on comparing different precursor choices rather than the performance of complete cells. By adopting a gravimetric FU, results can be directly traced to the inputs, energy demands, and emissions related to the production of a defined material amount, hence allowing for **fair comparisons across alternative materials** proposed for the same battery component. The main advantage of this approach is its **simplicity**, as it avoids including additional uncertainties linked to assumptions about final cell performance, electrode formulation, or system integration, which are still to be fully determined within the project.

However, a gravimetric FU does not capture the functional performance of the material in the battery system. Complete LCAs of batteries typically employ **1 kWh of delivered energy** as FU [10,11], since it reflects the final service provided by the device. This limitation is acknowledged, but at later stages of the project, when the prototype performance is validated, a shift towards a functional unit linked to energy storage and delivery will be implemented (see D4.4).

The next step is the **Life Cycle Inventory (LCI) analysis**. LCIs involve the compilation of data in terms of inputs and outputs of the system within the defined boundaries. **Inputs** are classified into those coming from nature: elemental flows of natural resources; and those coming from the Technosphere: materials and energy flows. On the other hand, **outputs** are divided into emissions: chemicals to air and chemicals to water; waste treatments: wastewater to treatment facilities and incineration; and products: main product and co-products.

A mass balance of the inputs and outputs of the system needs to be carried out during the LCI analysis to ensure its consistency. Similarly, an energy balance is also conducted for energy flows. All the input materials, water and energy carriers and all the output products, waste streams and emissions should be inventoried using primary data, if possible. Otherwise, it is necessary to gather this data from literature or patents.

Most of the inventories employed in this deliverable were extracted from literature sources, prioritizing the most commonly reported synthesis routes for each material or those for which detailed information was available. This approach was necessary given the vast number of materials assessed within SOLVE, where a streamlined strategy was required to ensure that the LCA remained feasible and not excessively time-consuming. In most cases, the synthesis processes considered correspond to conventional or widely adopted laboratory and industrial methods, thus allowing for a representative baseline comparison. For those precursors missing in conventional LCA databases, such as Ecoinvent v3.10, process models were either retrieved from literature sources or modelled in-house from patents or experimental procedures found in literature.

When the available literature was scarce or imprecise, partners were directly consulted in order to complement the inventories with primary data. This was the case for the ceramic fillers of the HSPE, where IKTS provided process-specific information for LAMP and Si@LAMP. Such contributions strengthen the reliability of the analysis by anchoring key materials to experimental data, while the rest of the inventories remain consistent with state-of-the-art practices reported in academic and patent literature.

In the **Life Cycle Impact Assessment (LCIA)** stage, LCI results are translated into environmental impacts by applying an impact assessment method. In this case, the European Commission recommends the Environmental Footprint (EF) 3.1 method over others due to its alignment with the European legal framework for harmonizing and standardizing environmental impact assessments, ensuring consistency and compliance across the European Union [12]. At this stage, 7 out of 16 impact categories were evaluated, which are presented in **Table 4**.

Table 4. Environmental Footprint 3.1 impact categories evaluated in the assessment.

Impact category	Acronym	Indicator	Unit
Climate change	CC	Radiative forcing as Global Warming Potential	kg CO _{2, eq.}
Ecotoxicity, freshwater	ETF	Comparative Toxic Unit for Ecosystems	CTU _e
Human toxicity, cancer	HT-C	Comparative Toxic Unit for humans	CTU _h
Human toxicity, non-cancer	HT-NC	Comparative Toxic Unit for humans	CTU _h
Resource use, fossils	RU-F	Abiotic resource depletion, fossil fuels	MJ
Resource use, minerals, and metals	RU-MM	Abiotic resource depletion, ultimate reserves	kg SB _{eq}
Water use	WU	User deprivation potential, deprivation-weighted water consumption	m ³ deprived

The selected categories are directly linked to critical issues such as greenhouse gas emissions, toxicity risks of solvents and transition metals, fossil energy dependence, raw material criticality, and water consumption in extraction and processing stages [11].

Finally, the **interpretation of results** focused on synthesizing the main findings and evaluating them against the previously defined goal and scope. In this deliverable, the comparison of environmental impacts across the selected categories was carried out for the alternative materials designed for the same battery component, as presented in *Chapter 4.4*.

2.2. SCORING SYSTEM

The development of a consolidated index can be a practical tool employed in decision-making, as it summarizes critical information into one or a few key numbers. This approach offers a quick overview of several constraints operating under different conditions.

Next, a scoring system implemented for the creation of a **materials scorecard** is described, adopting a methodology for the development of quantitative indicators. The developed scoring system consists of **four** different indicators, listed as follows:

- I. *Hazard level*
- II. *CRM content*
- III. *Cost*
- IV. *LCA single score*

A schematic overview of the framework is presented in **Figure 3**.

Figure 3: Framework for the development of materials scorecard.

Within SOLVE's materials scorecards, the comparisons are performed across the alternative options proposed for each specific battery component. This component-based approach ensures that the assessment directly supports the decision-making of developers especially at early stages, providing clear guidance on which option demonstrates higher performance under the SSbD framework.

Regarding the materials **hazard level**, a compilation of all the reagents used for the synthesis of the different materials was performed and complemented with the chemical hazard labels from the National Fire Protection Association (NFPA) [13]. This labelling scheme is usually indicated in safety datasheets provided

by suppliers, and it outlines the **health hazard**, **flammability**, and **instability** of chemicals on a scale from **0 (low hazard) to 4 (very high hazard)**, as depicted in **Figure 4**.

Figure 4: NFPA diamond and rating system [13].

To quantify the hazard of the chemical, a hazard index (I_{hazard}) is proposed in eq. (1):

$$I_{hazard} = \left[\frac{\sum_{i=1}^n HL_i}{n} \right] \cdot \bar{m}_{i,FU} \quad (1)$$

Where HL_i is the hazard level of precursor i for a specific hazard category, n is the number of categories assessed (equals 3 in this case – health, flammability, and instability), and $\bar{m}_{i,FU}$ is the mass fraction of precursor i per functional unit.

Second, the screening of materials proposed as alternatives for each battery component was performed in alignment with the list of critical and strategic materials proposed by the EC (see **Table 3**). The score for **material criticality** ($I_{criticality}$) was hence calculated by assessing the atomic mass of CRM input in the synthesis process ($m_{CRM,FU}$) per total mass in functional unit ($m_{TOT,FU}$), according to eq. (2):

$$I_{criticality} = \frac{\sum m_{CRM,FU}}{m_{TOT,FU}} \quad (2)$$

Continuing with the **cost** comparison for all materials was determined by multiplying their input mass during the synthesis ($m_{in,FU}$) by the scaled-up cost of raw materials (C_i), and measured in €/kg, as per eq. (3):

$$I_{cost} = \sum_{i=1}^n m_{in,FU} \cdot C_i \quad (3)$$

In order to calculate the cost of all the reagents employed in the synthesis of each battery component, the LCIs of the SOLVE system were utilized. For specific chemicals, cost data were collected from **Sigma Aldrich**, a well-known chemical company website with laboratory supply catalogues.

As previously referred the different costs (or selling prices) were estimated based on available price quotations from laboratory supply catalogues. A scaling-up method was used for the cost estimation of specialty chemicals, which are not usually produced in high volumes and whose information is often unavailable in conventional commodity price databases. The methodology was derived from Hart & Sommerfield, 1997 [14].

The price of these chemicals does not increase linearly with the quantity purchased, but rather logarithmically, hence the following process is employed to calculate their price in the quantities needed for the project. Prices for more than two volumes of the same chemical were collected, and a correlation formula was applied to extrapolate a bulk price of the selected chemical to the amount needed – see eqs. (4) and (5).

$$C = a \cdot Q^b \quad (4)$$

$$\log_{10} C = \log_{10} a + b \cdot \log_{10} Q \quad (5)$$

where, C refers to the unit cost of a given chemical in €/kg, Q to the quantity purchased (g), and a represents the cost coefficient corresponding to the unit price at a reference quantity. The parameter b represents the *scaling exponent* that characterises how the unit price decreases with increasing purchase volume. In practice, values of $b < 1$ indicate economies of scale: the larger the quantity bought, the lower the unit price due to bulk purchasing effects.

Finally, in rare cases where just one price quotation is available from the supplier page, a weighted average slope value of $b = 0.75$ is employed.

Lastly, the **environmental performance** of each material was determined through streamlined LCA, as results are presented in a comparative fashion in *Section 4.1*. Nevertheless, the materials scorecard includes an **LCA single score**, an indicator which employs factors (see Annex A2) from the EF 3.1 method for the **normalization and weighting of all sixteen impact categories** into a common dimensionless unit called “millipoint” (mPt) and aggregating them into a single value [15,16].

Therefore, the LCA single score for a given material is obtained through eq. (6):

$$LCA \text{ single score} = \sum_{i=1}^n Impact_i \cdot \frac{WF_i}{NF_i} \quad (6)$$

where, i indicates the impact category, WF represents the weighting factor, and NF the normalization factor.

Finally, all the values obtained in this analysis were **normalized** by dividing the maximum value reported for each indicator and alternative, in order to compare the scores on a **0-1 scale**. **The lower the overall score** after the sum of indicator, **the higher the performance** of the material, as it will be less hazardous, it will be produced at lower cost, its criticality will be lower, and its manufacture will pose lower environmental impacts.

2.3. RECYCLABILITY ASSESSMENT

The recyclability of a new developed battery system is an essential part to ensure the sustainability of the new product and achieve compliance with the recently established battery regulation EU 2023/1542. The recycling targets defined by the regulation must be achieved to design a suitable product that can target the European market. According to the Annex XII of the regulation the recycling targets for lithium batteries are defined as shown in **Table 5**.

The recycling efficiency (R_E) shall be calculated according to the procedures indicated in the EU regulation No 493/2012, as per eq. (7):

$$R_E = \frac{\sum m_{output}}{m_{input}} \cdot 100 \quad (7)$$

where, m_{output} are the output fractions taken into account for recycling and m_{input} are the input fractions in tonnes per calendar year. The regulation (EU) 2025/606 (supplementing the Regulation (EU) 2023/1542)

provides further details on the elements that may be considered for input and output fractions when calculating the recycling efficiency.

Table 5. Recycling targets for LIBs defined in the Annex XII of the EU 2023/1542 regulation [2].

	31/12/2025	31/12/2027	31/12/2030	31/12/2031
Average weight	65%	-	70%	-
Lithium	-	50%	-	80%
Nickel	-	90%	-	95%
Cobalt	-	90%	-	95%
Copper	-	90%	-	95%

Scope and materials will be established by defining a bill of materials with the masses of each of the components as well as the chemical composition and cell format and construction. This step is essential to identify the critical points towards developing a recycling strategy.

Once defined the bill of materials, a mapping of the recycling processes and technologies available at industrial scale or being currently implemented will be considered as potential route of End-of-Life of the SOLVE battery system while identifying the main challenges in terms of safety, performance and further downstream activities. Finally, the recycling route to be developed in the upcoming activities within SOLVE project will be defined.

3. DEVELOPMENT OF LIFE CYCLE INVENTORIES AND BOUNDARIES OF THE ASSESSMENT

This section details the procedure followed for the development of LCIs and the definition of the system boundaries for the assessment. In line with the comparative approach adopted in this deliverable, the analysis focuses on those cell components for which multiple material alternatives have been proposed.

The scheme provided in **Figure 5** shows all the battery components and sub-components in development within SOLVE. Subcomponents highlighted in pink have been excluded from the assessment at this stage, with the important note that they will be incorporated in **D4.4 – SSB impact assessment** at the end of the project (M48), when the final validation of the technology is carried out. The reasons behind these temporary exclusions are detailed below.

Figure 5: Battery components under development within SOLVE, with those shaded in pink being excluded so far from the assessment.

For the cathode **current collector**, only one option is under consideration: a carbon coated aluminium foil. Since the applied methodology relies on a comparative approach, its assessment would not provide additional insights at this stage, so its environmental contribution will be properly evaluated in D4.4, where the share of impact within the overall cell will be assessed.

For the **catholyte polymer**, three variants were initially considered: PVDF, PVDF-HFP, and PVDF-HSV. A LCI was built for PVDF, while PVDF-HFP and PVDF-HSV were intended to be modelled using primary data provided by Arkema due to the limited literature available. However, confidentiality restrictions have prevented the transmission of detailed synthesis data for the latter two at this stage. Given that only PVDF data could be reliably modelled, the comparative approach could not be maintained, and the polymeric catholyte has therefore been excluded at this point. The same reasoning applies to the polymer of the hybrid solid polymer-based electrolyte, where only PVDF was proposed as material alternative. These materials will be fully assessed in D4.4 once the necessary datasets are accessible.

Two **anodic side configurations** were proposed: LiM and AF. At the current stage, most of these subcomponents have not been included due to their higher structural complexity and the ongoing experimental optimization of their layer compositions. Nevertheless, alternatives to the barrier layer of the

LiM configuration were assessed, as sufficient data were available to enable a meaningful comparison. Both LiM and AF full configurations will be comprehensively included in the LCA at the validation stage.

With respect to the **energy consumption** data employed during the modelling of the different material alternatives, it has been excluded in cases where reliable and process-specific data are not available. Given the streamlined nature of the LCA conducted at this phase of the project, the analysis focuses primarily on the environmental impacts of the raw materials required for each synthesis route, as these are expected to be the dominant contributors to the overall environmental impact.

A key reason for this approach is that most energy consumption values reported in the literature refer to laboratory-scale syntheses, which tend to be significantly overestimated compared to industrially relevant scenarios. As such, these values may not be representative of the actual energy demands of scaled-up processes, and their inclusion could distort the outcome of the comparative assessment. Nonetheless, whenever precise and consistent energy consumption data were available for all material alternatives within a given component category, such information was duly included into the assessment to ensure a fair comparison across options. This assumption enables a preliminary screening of environmental impacts that prioritizes data consistency and comparability.

A more detailed quantification of energy consumption will be addressed in the final LCA, where such impacts will be systematically evaluated and mitigation strategies proposed if any process is identified as a potential environmental hotspot.

Finally, it is worth noting that the environmental impacts associated with different **processing routes** of the materials (e.g., wet-slurry coating versus dry-extrusion lamination for the cathode) will be evaluated at a later stage of the project. This decision is motivated by the fact that such an assessment becomes meaningful only once the final cell configuration is defined and process data at relevant scale are available, which will be achieved in WP3. At that point, the modelling of processing steps will provide a more realistic representation of the environmental performance, avoiding premature estimations based on laboratory-scale procedures that do not reflect industrial practice.

Table 6 presents a summary with all materials to be assessed in defined for Deliverable 1.3, listing all assessed components and subcomponents together with their respective material options. The last column indicates whether energy consumption was included in the different calculations.

Table 6. List of materials assessed in SOLVE's D1.3.

Component	Sub-component	Option 1	Option 2	Option 3	Energy considered?
High-loading solid-state cathode	Powder	NMC 85:5:10 (LiM-SSB)	Li-rich NMC (AF-SSB)	-	No
	Coating	Li ₃ BO ₃	Li ₂ ZrO ₃	LATP	No
	Conductive additives	Carbon black	VGCF	-	Yes
	Li salts	LiTFSI	LiFSI	LiBOB	No
	Plasticiser	PYR14TFSI	PYR14FSI	-	Yes
Hybrid solid polymer-based electrolyte	Li salts	LiTFSI	LiFSI	LiBOB	No
	Plasticiser	PYR14TFSI	PYR14FSI	-	Yes
	Ceramic filler	LATP	Si@LATP	-	No
LiM anode	Barrier layer	LLZO	Li ₃ N	LiPON	No

In summary, the temporary exclusions are not intended to undermine the robustness of the current analysis but rather to ensure consistency and comparability across the assessed materials. By focusing on components with multiple alternatives and accessible data, this deliverable provides a sound basis for early-stage eco-design decisions, while acknowledging that the full environmental performance of all cell subcomponents will be captured in Deliverable D4.4.

4. SUSTAINABILITY ASSESSMENT OF ALTERNATIVES

4.1. LIFE CYCLE IMPACT ASSESSMENT

4.1.1. HIGH-LOADING SOLID-STATE CATHODE

The cathode is widely recognised as the main environmental hotspot in conventional lithium-ion batteries, largely due to the extraction and processing of transition metals and the energy-intensive synthesis routes required for their active materials. For this reason, an exhaustive analysis of the high-loading solid-state cathode has been assessed in order to identify the main environmental hotspots and highlight potential directions for reducing associated burdens.

As illustrated in **Figure 5**, the cathode is composed of both active and inactive material subcomponents. The evaluation conducted in this deliverable covers the active material powder and coating, as well as the inactive materials including conductive additives, lithium salts, and plasticisers. This provides a comprehensive picture of the main contributors to the environmental impacts of the cathode architecture developed within SOLVE.

CAM powder

For the cathode active material (CAM) powder, two different formulations are proposed within SOLVE, each tailored to the requirements of the two cell architectures under development. For the **LiM-SSB, NMC 85:5:10** ($LiNi_{0.85}Mn_{0.05}Co_{0.10}O_2$) was selected, whereas for the **AF-SSB**, a **Li-rich NMC** ($Li_{1.2}Ni_{0.1}Mn_{0.6}Co_{0.1}O_2$) formulation was adopted. It is worth mentioning that these two chemistries are not competing alternatives, since both configurations will be employed in parallel throughout the project. Therefore, just in this case, the comparison of their cradle-to-gate impacts does not serve the purpose of selecting one over the other, but rather to understand their relative environmental profiles.

To ensure a fairer comparison between the two cathode chemistries, the **functional unit** chosen for comparison is **1 mAh** of theoretical capacity. While a mass-based analysis provides an initial understanding of material-level burdens, it does not capture the actual functionality of the active material within the cell. Since Li-rich NMC is typically associated with a slightly higher theoretical capacity than NMC 85:5:10 (~220 mAh/g vs. ~200 mAh/g), the mass required to deliver the same energy capacity at the cell level is reduced. Consequently, considering capacity as the functional unit allows for a more meaningful evaluation of the environmental performance of both materials in the context of their intended application in the battery.

For NMC 85:5:10, the life cycle inventory of NMC 811 was taken as a proxy following a **co-precipitation synthesis route** [17]. It was selected because the underlying chemistry and production pathway of NMC 85:5:10 are practically the same as those of NMC 811, both being high-nickel NMC cathodes produced through the same industrial co-precipitation method. The main difference lies in the specific Ni:Mn:Co ratio, which does not significantly affect the foreground synthesis process steps, making NMC 811 a robust proxy for modelling the environmental profile of NMC 85:5:10. On the other hand, Li-rich NMC was modelled based on a **combustion synthesis route** in which metal nitrates of lithium, nickel, manganese, and cobalt are combined with urea and glycine as fuel and reducing agents, respectively [18].

Figure 6 shows the cradle-to-gate environmental impact comparison between the two proposed CAM powders.

As seen in **Figure 6**, **Li-rich NMC** exhibits the highest environmental impacts in **4 out of 7** impact categories, namely climate change (CC), freshwater ecotoxicity (ETF), cancerous human toxicity (HT-C), and resource use of fossils (RU-F). Particular attention should be given to CC and ETF, where the conventional NMC 85:5:10 accounts for only 73% and 69% of the impacts of Li-rich NMC, respectively. In contrast, NMC 85:5:10 records the highest burdens in non-cancerous human toxicity (HT-NC) and resource use of minerals and metals (RU-MM), where the Li-rich alternative pose 74% and 70% of those relative impacts.

Figure 6: Cradle-to-gate environmental impact comparison per 1 mAh of capacity of the two proposed CAM powder alternatives: Li-rich NMC and NMC 85:5:10. Impact categories: Climate change (CC); Ecotoxicity, freshwater (ETF); Human toxicity, cancer (HT-C); Human toxicity, non-cancer (HT-NC); Resource use, fossils (RU-F); Resource use, minerals and metals (RU-MM); Water use (WU).

In addition, the environmental results of each cathode chemistry are disaggregated to identify the main hotspots across impact categories. Since the two CAM options are not direct substitutes but rather complementary research directions within the project, it is more meaningful to analyse their environmental profiles individually rather than framing them as competing alternatives. This approach allows for a clearer understanding of the specific drivers of impacts in each case and provides targeted insights for future optimisation efforts.

Thus, **Figure 7** presents the environmental impact breakdown of Li-rich NMC powder. As seen in **Figure 7**, it can be outlined that the main environmental hotspots associated with the production of Li-rich NMC powder are associated with the **metal nitrate precursors** employed in the synthesis. In particular, **cobalt nitrate** emerges as the main contributor among most impact categories, accounting for 54% of the overall impacts in HT-NC; 59% in RU-MM; and 61% in WU. These results reflect the high environmental burden of cobalt extraction and refining, which are well-known for being hotspots in LIB supply chains.

Nickel nitrate is another relevant hotspot, especially in HT-NC (21%) and RU-MM (29%), where it represents the second most important contributor after cobalt nitrate. Meanwhile, **lithium nitrate** poses strong influence in CC (24%) and RU-F (21%), consistent with the high energy requirements and CO₂ emissions associated with lithium compound production.

Other precursors such as **manganese nitrate** stand out in HT-C (21%), being the second contributor within that category, while the use of **glycine** as reducing agent is the main environmental driver with respect to ETF, accounting for 37% of the overall impacts.

Finally, **direct CO₂ emissions** generated during the combustion process add about 5% to the climate change category, further emphasizing the relevance of energy and process emissions in the overall profile.

Figure 7: Environmental impact breakdown of Li-rich NMC powder. Impact categories: Climate change (CC); Ecotoxicity, freshwater (ETF); Human toxicity, cancer (HT-C); Human toxicity, non-cancer (HT-NC); Resource use, fossils (RU-F); Resource use, minerals and metals (RU-MM); Water use (WU).

Next, **Figure 8** present the environmental impact breakdown for the NMC 85:5:10 composition.

Figure 8: Environmental impact breakdown of NMC 85:5:10. Impact categories: Climate change (CC); Ecotoxicity, freshwater (ETF); Human toxicity, cancer (HT-C); Human toxicity, non-cancer (HT-NC); Resource use, fossils (RU-F); Resource use, minerals and metals (RU-MM); Water use (WU).

As seen in **Figure 8**, the **NMC hydroxide precursor** is clearly more impactful than lithium hydroxide across all impact categories, accounting for over 75% of the overall impacts in each one of them. Therefore, a zoom in is carried out in **Figure 9** to disaggregate and better visualise the origin of these high environmental burdens.

Figure 9: Environmental impact breakdown of $\text{NMC}(\text{OH})_2$ precursor. Impact categories: Climate change (CC); Ecotoxicity, freshwater (ETF); Human toxicity, cancer (HT-C); Human toxicity, non-cancer (HT-NC); Resource use, fossils (RU-F); Resource use, minerals and metals (RU-MM); Water use (WU).

As shown in **Figure 9**, the impact of the production of the NMC precursor is clearly dominated by the use of **nickel sulfate** across all impact categories, ranging from 47% to 81% in all categories. The next main contributor is **cobalt sulfate**, contributing between 16-24%, depending on the category, with particularly high relevance in climate change (CC), freshwater ecotoxicity (ETF), and water use (WU). Natural gas, used as an energy source, is another relevant contributor, accounting for ~16% of CC impacts and ~14% of fossil resource use (RU-F), linking the process directly to upstream energy emissions.

Outputs from the process also add measurable burdens. Wastewater treatment alone contributes 23% to ETF, while sodium sulfate disposal represents 6-8% of total impacts in several categories. Interestingly, the inventory shows a negative contribution for wastewater in the water use category (-49%), which stems from modelling assumptions in Ecoinvent where wastewater treatment is credited with partial water return to the environment.

Overall, the results show that in both Li-rich NMC and NMC 85:5:10, the **metal precursors** – particularly cobalt- and nickel-based salts – **are the dominant contributors** to the environmental impacts across most of impact categories. This suggests that improving the sustainability of these chemistries requires measures such as optimising precursor composition (e.g., further reducing cobalt content), developing less energy-intensive synthesis routes, or improving precursor yields to minimise waste. In addition, advancing recycling strategies to recover critical metals could help mitigate the burdens associated with their primary extraction.

4.1.1.1. Coating

In order to enhance interfacial stability and mitigate side reactions at the cathode-electrolyte interface, three alternatives were proposed for the cathode coating of both LiM- and AF-SSB cell architectures: **lithium aluminium titanium phosphate or LAMP** ($Li_{1.3}Al_{0.3}Ti_{1.7}(PO_4)_3$); modelled according to a solid-state reaction route developed by IKTS [19]; **lithium zirconate** (Li_2ZrO_3), also modelled via a solid-state method [20]; and **lithium borate** (Li_3BO_3), whose LCI was built following a mechanochemical synthesis procedure [21]. Each of them represents a different chemical family since borates and zirconates are typically considered for their ionic conductivity and stability, while LAMP is a NASICON-type ceramic with broader potential functionalities (e.g., as ceramic filler in the electrolyte).

Figure 10 presents the cradle-to-gate environmental impacts for the three proposed cathode coatings.

Figure 10: Cradle-to-gate environmental impact comparison of the three proposed cathode coating alternatives: LAMP, Li_2ZrO_3 , and Li_3BO_3 . Impact categories: Climate change (CC); Ecotoxicity, freshwater (ETF); Human toxicity, cancer (HT-C); Human toxicity, non-cancer (HT-NC); Resource use, fossils (RU-F); Resource use, minerals and metals (RU-MM); Water use (WU).

Lithium borate dominates all impact categories, with the exception of water use, where impacts are similar for the three assessed alternatives. The main impact contributor in most categories is the **lithium hydroxide** employed as reagent, which poses a significant bigger environmental burden in comparison with the lithium source used during the synthesis of lithium borate and LAMP - lithium carbonate in both cases. On the other hand, **boric acid** is the main responsible for such high impacts in the **resource use of minerals and metals (RU-MM)** category, where the other two coatings represent less than 10% of their impacts.

Lithium zirconate performs better than lithium borate in every impact category, but still exhibits a non-negligible environmental footprint, especially in categories such as CC, HT-C, or RU-F. By contrast, **LAMP** displays the lowest environmental profile overall, with substantially reduced contributions in human toxicity (both cancerous and non-cancerous) and climate change.

These results show that **LAMP emerges as the most sustainable option** among those assessed, while Li_3BO_3 carries the largest environmental burden and should therefore be dismissed. Nevertheless, it is worth

mentioning that the coating function is highly specific to the electrochemical configuration, i.e., materials are not interchangeable without implications regarding compatibility and performance. Therefore, the interpretation of these LCA results must be integrated with electrochemical validation to ensure that options with lower environmental profiles can still deliver the required functionality at cell level.

4.1.1.2. Conductive additives

In SOLVE's cell design, the catholyte is composed of the polymer, the lithium salts and the plasticiser, providing ionic conductivity within the cathode. However, **conductive additives** must be incorporated into the cathode composite to facilitate electron transport between the CAM particles and the current collector.

Three alternatives were initially proposed: **C45**, **C65**, and **vapor-grown carbon fibres (VGCF)**. Given that C45 and C65 are two grades of carbon black differing mainly in particle size, their cradle-to-gate environmental impacts can be reasonably assumed to be similar. Therefore, they were both represented by the **carbon black** Ecoinvent dataset. For VGCF, its synthesis was modelled according to the process reported in [22].

Figure 11 shows the cradle-to-gate environmental impact comparison between carbon black and VGCF.

Figure 11: Cradle-to-gate environmental impact comparison of the two proposed cathode conductive additives: carbon black and vapor grown carbon fibres (VGCF). Impact categories: Climate change (CC); Ecotoxicity, freshwater (ETF); Human toxicity, cancer (HT-C); Human toxicity, non-cancer (HT-NC); Resource use, fossils (RU-F); Resource use, minerals and metals (RU-MM); Water use (WU).

With the results shown in **Figure 11**, it is immediately clear that **VGCF exhibits much higher environmental burdens across all impact categories** compared to carbon black. The LCIA breakdown indicates that the dominant driver is **electricity consumption**, which accounts for between 65-72% of the total impacts depending on the category. This reflects the extremely energy-intensive nature of the VGCF production process, involving the decomposition of hydrocarbons (e.g., ethylene, hexane) in the presence of catalysts under controlled conditions.

From an eco-design perspective, this finding must be interpreted in light of the different scales at which both materials were modelled. The VGCF synthesis process was based on laboratory- or pilot-scale data, while the carbon black dataset from Ecoinvent represents industrial-scale production. This discrepancy largely explains the pronounced differences observed in their environmental performance within this assessment. Although VGCF manufacturing is inherently energy-intensive due to the high-temperature conditions required for vapor-phase carbon deposition, the efficiency gains achievable at industrial scale – such as optimised reactor design, heat recovery, and improved process integration – would substantially reduce its relative impacts. Therefore, while the current results clearly favour carbon black, the gap between both materials would likely narrow under real industrial conditions.

4.1.1.3. Lithium salts

Lithium salts are a critical component in the catholyte as they ensure a proper Li⁺ transport within the polymer matrix. In SOLVE, three alternatives were modelled: lithium bis(oxolato)borate, or **LiBOB** [23]; lithium bis(trifluoromethanesulfonyl)imide, or **LiTFSI** [24]; and lithium bis(fluorosulfonyl)imide, or **LiFSI** [25]. Their comparative cradle-to-gate are presented in **Figure 12**.

Figure 12: Cradle-to-gate environmental impact comparison of the three proposed lithium salts for the catholyte: LiBOB, LiTFSI, and LiFSI. Impact categories: Climate change (CC); Ecotoxicity, freshwater (ETF); Human toxicity, cancer (HT-C); Human toxicity, non-cancer (HT-NC); Resource use, fossils (RU-F); Resource use, minerals and metals (RU-MM); Water use (WU).

As observed in **Figure 12**, **LiFSI** emerges as the **most sustainable** option, displaying consistently lower impacts than the other two alternatives across all categories, with the exception of water use, where it presents the highest environmental footprint. By contrast, **LiTFSI** seems to be the main contributor in **4 out of 7** impact categories. This is due to the fact that LiTFSI requires large amounts of methylchloride as feedstock, whose production is high energy-intensive, fossil-based, and contributes significantly to human toxicity (non-cancerous effects).

On the other hand, **LiBOB** presents a mixed environmental profile. It avoids the use of fluorine during its synthesis, but it is **penalised in human toxicity (cancer) and resource use – minerals and metals**. This

is largely due to the reliance on **boric acid**, which is the main driver in the RU-MM category, and oxalic acid. Large amounts of the latter are used during the synthesis, making it the main environmental hotspot in the rest of categories.

In summary, while LiBOB is not the worst option and could theoretically serve as a fluorine-free alternative, **LiFSI stands out as the most suitable lithium salt** from an environmental perspective, provided that the water use burden can be mitigated or is less critical in the overall system balance.

4.1.1.4. Plasticiser

Four ionic liquids were initially considered as potential plasticisers for the catholyte:

- **PYR13TFSI** (*N-propyl-N-methylpyrrolidinium bis(trifluoromethanesulfonyl)imide*)
- **PYR13FSI** (*N-propyl-N-methylpyrrolidinium bis(fluorosulfonyl)imide*)
- **PYR14TFSI** (*N-butyl-N-methylpyrrolidinium bis(trifluoromethanesulfonyl)imide*)
- **PYR14FSI** (*N-butyl-N-methylpyrrolidinium bis(fluorosulfonyl)imide*)

Since the difference between the PYR13 and PYR14 family lies only in the alkyl chain length of the pyrrolidinium cation (N-propyl vs. N-butyl), the environmental disparities between them were expected to be minimal compared to the influence of the anion. Indeed, their synthesis route are dominated by the production of the anion precursor salts (TFSI⁻ and FSI⁻), whose burdens outweigh the relatively small variations in the pyrrolidinium cations. For this reason, and to avoid redundancy, the comparison was restricted to **PYR14TFSI** and **PYR14FSI**. Their respective LCIs were retrieved from literature ([26,27]) and their relative cradle-to-gate impacts per kg of material produced are presented in **Figure 13**.

Figure 13: Cradle-to-gate environmental impact comparison of the two proposed cathode plasticisers: PYR14TFSI and PYR14FSI. Impact categories: Climate change (CC); Ecotoxicity, freshwater (ETF); Human toxicity, cancer (HT-C); Human toxicity, non-cancer (HT-NC); Resource use, fossils (RU-F); Resource use, minerals and metals (RU-MM); Water use (WU).

The results presented in **Figure 13** state that the two assessed options exhibit different impact profiles. On the one hand, **PYR14FSI** performs better in CC and RU-F – with practically half of the PYR14TFSI impacts within those categories – and in ETF. On the other hand, **PYR14TFSI** outperforms PYR14FSI in the other four impact categories (both human toxicities, RU-MM, and WU).

It should be noted that in the case of PYR14TFSI, the negative value obtained in HT-NC results from the application of **system expansion**. In both models (also for PYR14FSI), the co-product **lithium bromide** is credited with avoiding the production of the equivalent amount and potential generated emissions, which in turn avoids the associated toxicity burdens. As a consequence, the avoided burden outweighs the actual emissions of the process, producing a negative value.

In summary, **PYR14FSI** appears as the **more sustainable option when prioritising climate-related and fossil resource indicators**, although this comes at the cost of higher toxicity- and resource-related scores. **PYR14TFSI**, while more favourable in RU-MM and toxicity (under system expansion assumptions), is penalised by its reliance on LiTFSI synthesis, dominated by methylchloride burdens (as explained in Section 4.1.1.3). From an eco-design perspective, efforts to reduce the dependence on chlorinated organics in the LiTFSI route or to harmonise the handling of co-products would improve the robustness of the comparison. Nonetheless, the present results clearly indicate that the **choice of anion (FSI vs. TFSI) is the key driver** of the environmental profile of pyrrolidinium-based plasticisers.

4.1.2. HYBRID SOLID POLYMER-BASED ELECTROLYTE

The hybrid solid polymer electrolyte (HSPE) is a central element of the SOLVE cell architecture, enabling a stable ion transport between the electrodes while providing the safety and mechanical stability advantages of solid-state systems compared to conventional liquid electrolytes. By combining a polymer matrix with selected additives, the HSPE is designed to suppress Li dendrites growth, maintain reliable interfacial contact, and enable high cycling stability.

More specifically, the HSPE formulation comprises a polymer matrix, a lithium salt, a plasticiser, and a ceramic filler. For the Li salts and plasticiser, the same options have already been assessed for the cathode formulation (see *Sections 4.1.1.3* and *4.1.1.4*), so this section focuses specifically on the comparison of the **ceramic filler** alternatives, providing valuable insights about the main point of differentiation in terms of environmental performance within the HSPE.

Ceramic filler

The ceramic filler within the HSPE plays a crucial role in enhancing the mechanical strength of the polymer matrix and in improving ionic conductivity by providing pathways for Li-ion transport. It is therefore an essential subcomponent to ensure the stability and electrochemical performance of the HSPE. In this study, two alternatives were proposed by IKTS: **LATP** and **silane-modified LATP (Si@LATP)**. For the latter, the modification with a Si-based coating aims to improve interfacial compatibility and reduce internal resistance.

Both fillers were modelled from the synthesis procedure developed by IKTS, with Si@LATP based on the process reported in [28]. **LATP** was synthesized via a solid-state reaction (see *Section 4.1.1.1*). For the considered **Si@LATP** synthesis route, LATP particles are immersed in a solution containing ethanol, acetic acid, and (3-Aminopropyl)trimethoxysilane or APTMS, the silane precursor, followed by stirring, centrifugation, and drying processes.

Next, **Figure 14** shows the environmental impact comparison of the two proposed ceramic fillers.

Figure 14. Cradle-to-gate environmental impact comparison of the two proposed HSPE ceramic fillers: LATP and Si@LATP. Impact categories: Climate change (CC); Ecotoxicity, freshwater (ETF); Human toxicity, cancer (HT-C); Human toxicity, non-cancer (HT-NC); Resource use, fossils (RU-F); Resource use, minerals and metals (RU-MM); Water use (WU).

As observed in **Figure 14**, **Si@LATP** exhibit **significantly higher environmental impacts across all impact categories**, especially in CC, HT-C, and RU-F, where LATP impacts pose less than 5% of its silane-modified counterpart impacts. This outcome can be explained by its synthesis route: since 1 kg of LATP is required as feedstock in order to produce 1 kg of silane-modified LATP, its environmental load is fully embedded in the Si@LATP inventory, and the addition of solvents and reagents for the modification step substantially increases the cradle-to-gate impacts. In particular, the large amounts of **ethanol** – both for the preparation of the APTMS solution and for washing – are the main responsible in most of the impact categories, followed by the contribution of APTMS, with especial attention to cancerous human toxicity.

Overall, while the surface modification of LATP with silane may bring potential electrochemical performance benefits, the environmental trade-off is considerable. From a sustainability perspective, the additional processing steps and solvent use make Si@LATP a significantly less favourable option than unmodified LATP.

4.1.3. Lithium metal anode

As already mentioned in *Section 3*, insufficient data were available to conduct a comprehensive assessment of the two anodic side configurations at this stage of the project (LiM and AF). For this reason, the present deliverable focuses only on the **barrier layer** alternatives proposed for the LiM configuration, for which LCIs could be built. The barrier layer is deposited via Pulsed Laser Deposition (PLD) on Li metal with the goal of stabilising the interface with the HSPE by suppressing dendrite formation, reducing parasitic side reactions, and improving the durability of the anode-electrolyte contact. The following subsection presents the environmental assessment of the barrier layer materials proposed within SOLVE.

Barrier layer

Three different alternatives were proposed as barrier layer materials for the LIM anode configuration. First, **lithium nitride** (Li_3N) was modelled following the process reported in [29], where a Li metal foil is exposed to nitrogen within a glovebox to promote its conversion into lithium nitride. Second, **lithium lanthanum zirconium oxide or LLZO** ($Li_7La_3Zr_2O_{12}$) was modelled employing the solid-state synthesis route described in [19]. Finally, **lithium phosphorus oxynitride or LiPON** was inventoried according to the synthesis proposed in [30].

Next, **Figure 15** shows the environmental impact comparison of the three considered barriers for the lithium metal anode.

Figure 15: Cradle-to-gate environmental impact comparison of the three proposed LIM anode barrier layers: Li_3N , LLZO, and LiPON. Impact categories: Climate change (CC); Ecotoxicity, freshwater (ETF); Human toxicity, cancer (HT-C); Human toxicity, non-cancer (HT-NC); Resource use, fossils (RU-F); Resource use, minerals and metals (RU-MM); Water use (WU).

Among the assessed alternatives in **Figure 15**, **lithium nitride** clearly stands out as the **least sustainable option**, presenting the highest impacts in **6 out of 7** categories, with the exception of freshwater ecotoxicity, where LLZO dominates. This is primarily due to the use of lithium metal as feedstock, which already carries high environmental burdens, especially regarding its extraction and processing. The conversion process to Li_3N , although relatively simple in laboratory conditions, inherits large upstream impacts associated with metallic lithium production, making this material environmentally disadvantageous compared to LLZO and LiPON.

In contrast, and as already mentioned, **LLZO** appears to be the most sustainable option overall, showing the lowest impacts in almost every category except for ETF, where it dominates due to use of large amounts of lithium oxide during its synthesis. LiPON occupies an intermediate position between the two, with impacts consistently higher than LLZO but still significantly lower than Li_3N .

4.2. HAZARD ASSESSMENT

Assessing the environmental, health, and safety (EHS) characteristics of the materials involved is a critical step in evaluating the sustainability of a process and is fully aligned with the green chemistry principles. Beyond environmental performance, EHS considerations also influence equipment design, choice of construction materials, chemical storage and handling requirements, production throughput, and overall process robustness. While highly reactive or hazardous substances are routinely used in industry under controlled conditions, they demand stringent precautions during synthesis, storage, transportation, and use to avoid accidents or unintended reactions. From a sustainability perspective, it is preferable to minimise or eliminate the use of harmful substances whenever possible, rather than relying on their End-of-Life treatment, which inevitably requires additional energy and material resources [31].

A major challenge with EHS metrics is the limited availability of comprehensive data and databases, despite legislative initiatives like the EU's REACH (Registration, Evaluation, Authorization, and Restriction of Chemicals) address this issue. It is also important to differentiate between risk and hazard. In some cases, using a substance with low inherent hazard in large quantities can pose more significant risks than using a more hazardous material in smaller amounts. The concept of risk is derived from the combination of a material's inherent hazard and the probability of exposure or occurrence.

Furthermore, unstable compounds are more prone to be used than less reactive and less hazardous ones since the former tend to react more readily and facilitate the completion of a reaction, both thermodynamically and kinetically, posing an additional challenge. Thus, it is necessary to be careful when handling unstable compounds, as they typically possess inherent hazards which need to be assessed and mitigated as far as possible [32].

On the other hand, the use of varied equipment in handling hazardous materials can present distinctive risks to the external environment and cannot go unnoticed, particularly when scaling up the process. For example, certain equipment types such as reactors may carry the risk of leakage or explosion when specific chemical substances are involved, subsequently leading to contamination of the surrounding water and atmosphere [33].

Hazard level classification of all precursors considered to build the different Life Cycle Inventories are presented in Annex A1 as for NFPA labelling scheme. As explained in *Section 2.2*, the hazard indicator (I_{hazard}) is obtained through eq. (1). As an example, hazard indicator calculation sequence of LATP cathode coating is presented in **Table 7**.

Table 7. Hazard scoring calculation sequence for LATP.

SUBSTANCE	MASS (kg)	MASS FRACTION	HAZARD LEVEL			I_{hazard}
			Health	Flammability	Instability	
Aluminium oxide	0.040	0.03	1	0	0	$9.38 \cdot 10^{-3}$
Lithium carbonate	0.125	0.09	1	0	0	0.030
Ammonium dihydrogen phosphate	0.897	0.63	1	0	0	0.211
Titanium dioxide	0.353	0.25	1	0	0	0.083
TOTAL	1.41	1.00				0.333

Therefore, the **material hazard index for LATP is 0.333**. The same calculation process is carried out for the rest of components within the same component family (i.e., cathode coating in this case), resulting in the outputs presented in **Table 8**. Once the scoring is obtained for each material, the values are normalized in order to compare the scores on a 0-1 scale. As observed in this case, the most hazardous material is **lithium borate**.

Table 8. Cathode coating materials hazard index.

MATERIAL	I_{hazard}	NORMALISED SCORE
LATP	0.33	0.33
Li_2ZrO_3	0.54	0.54
Li_3BO_3	1.00	1.00

4.3. CRITICALITY ASSESSMENT

The first step in the assessment of the criticality carried out in SOLVE involved a screening of the main raw materials employed in the different battery subcomponents following the CRM list [5], already presented in Table 3. The aim was to identify potential risks in terms of supply security and economic importance, which are key aspects for the long-term sustainability and scalability of SSB technologies. The following analysis is based on information retrieved from the **Raw Materials Information System (RMIS)**, which provide the most up-to-date and harmonised data on global extraction, production shares, and supply risk indicators for critical materials [34].

Several transition metals widely used in CAMs, such as **cobalt**, **nickel**, and **manganese** were included in the assessment, as they are essential materials for lithium-ion batteries. Among them, cobalt is currently classified as both critical and strategic, given its high supply risk and the concentration of production in the Democratic Republic of Congo (around 70% of global output), which clearly is a sign of a poor supply chain governance. Nickel is also listed as critical and strategic due to its indispensable role in the energy transition and its use in high-performance battery chemistries; and manganese owns a significant role in steel production and batteries, with South Africa and Gabon being the leading suppliers.

Lithium, central to both the cathode and electrolyte formulations considered in SOLVE, remains one of the most relevant CRMs. It is classified as both critical and strategic, reflecting its indispensable role in energy storage applications and the strong concentration of processing capacity in a few countries, particularly Australia and Chile.

Other elements relevant within SOLVE's cell architecture appear in the CRM list. Phosphorus precursors, essential for coatings, derive from **phosphate rock**, which is considered critical due to its essential role in fertilisers and limited geographical availability. **Fluorine** sources (e.g., fluor spar), necessary for fluorinated salts and ionic liquids, are likewise listed as critical, with China being the main global producer. In the case of LATP-type fillers, zirconium and titanium are currently not listed as CRMs, but their supply stability is closely monitored given their use in advanced ceramics and high-tech applications.

Boron, present in materials such as LiBOB and Li_3BO_3 , is also included in the 2024 CRM list due to its highly concentrated supply, with Turkey holding the majority of global reserves and production – 87% and 48% respectively. This dependency creates potential supply risks despite its widespread industrial applications.

Finally, **lanthanum**, present in LLZO, belongs to the group of Light Rare Earth Elements (LREEs) and is also classified as critical, as rare earth production is overwhelmingly dominated by China (over 57%), which controls both mining and refining capacities, raising concerns over long-term supply security.

Overall, the screening confirms that many of the core materials used in the SOLVE technologies fall within the scope of the CRM framework, underlining the importance of considering criticality alongside environmental performance in the design of next-generation solid-state batteries.

In the same way as in the hazard assessment, the calculation sequence of cathode coatings' criticality index ($I_{\text{criticality}}$) is shown in **Table 9** as an example. Eq. (2) from Section 2.2 was employed and the results were obtained with the data reported in the different LCIs. It is worth mentioning that the mass of each CRM was calculated from stoichiometric ratios.

Table 9. Raw materials criticality scoring calculation sequence for cathode coatings.

MATERIAL	$m_{TOT, FU}$ (kg)	Element	$m_{Element}$ (kg)	CRM	$m_{CRM, FU}$ (kg)	$I_{criticality}$
LATP	1.00	Al	0.021	Aluminium	0.021	1.89
		Li	0.024	Lithium	0.024	
		P	0.242	Phosphate rock	1.85	
Li_2ZrO_3	1.00	Li	0.098	Lithium	0.098	0.098
Li_3BO_3	1.00	Li	0.281	Lithium	0.281	0.427
		B	0.146	Boron	0.146	

Taking LATP as an example, it is observed that it is composed of three CRMs, which are aluminium, lithium, and phosphate rock. In order to calculate the mass of each CRM, it is necessary to detect the chemical element that is present in the CRM (e.g., phosphorus in phosphate rock) in the first place. Enriched phosphate rock approximately contains 30% of P_2O_5 [35] and P content in P_2O_5 is obtained from their molecular weights ($M_{w_{P_2O_5}} = 142 \frac{g}{mol}$; $M_{w_P} = 31 \frac{g}{mol}$) employing eq. (8).

$$\% P \text{ content in } P_2O_5 = \frac{2 \cdot M_{w_P}}{M_{w_{P_2O_5}}} \cdot 100 = 43.7\% \quad (8)$$

Therefore, phosphate rock mass ($m_{phosphate\ rock}$) is calculated through (9):

$$m_{phosphate\ rock} = 0.242 \text{ kg } P \cdot \frac{1 \text{ kg } P_2O_5}{0.437 \text{ kg } P} \cdot \frac{1 \text{ kg phosphate rock}}{0.3 \text{ kg } P_2O_5} = 1.85 \text{ kg} \quad (9)$$

In the case of aluminium and lithium, the mass of the element is the same as that of the CRM, as nickel itself is considered a CRM. Therefore, no intermediate calculations are necessary. The calculation process is analogous for the remaining battery components.

Finally, the scored is normalised in the same way as in the hazard index, being **lithium zirconate** the material with the **lowest criticality score**, as seen in **Table 10**, meaning that it is the best option regarding this matter. This is due to the fact that the only CRM it relies on is lithium, and it is also present in a small amount.

Table 10: Cathode coating materials' criticality indexes and normalized scores.

MATERIAL	$I_{criticality}$	NORMALISED SCORE
LATP	1.89	1.00
Li_2ZrO_3	0.10	0.05
Li_3BO_3	0.43	0.23

4.4. COST ASSESSMENT

The cost assessment presented in this deliverable provides an indicative estimation of the relative economic performance of the assessed materials. As explained in *Section 2.2*, the considered prices correspond to bulk-scale market values, representing the acquisition cost of raw materials typically available for industrial

use rather than laboratory-grade prices. Therefore, while the analysis does not yet reflect a fully optimised large-scale production environment, it offers a realistic and comparable baseline to guide early material selection.

It is important to highlight that material costs in industrial manufacturing do not scale linearly. When moving towards commercial production, various factors – such as economies of scale, synthesis route optimisation, process yields, and supply chain logistics – can significantly influence the final cost structure. Consequently, the current analysis should be regarded as a preliminary economic screening of the proposed materials, aimed at identifying those with potentially lower cost implications within the overall manufacturing process.

The cost index (I_{cost}) for each material alternative assessed in SOLVE was calculated following eq. (3), based on the total cost of its input materials and precursors. As an example, **Table 11** presents the cost calculation sequence for LATP, where the total cost of its synthesis, considering bulk prices for all reagents, amounts to **46.04 €/kg**.

Table 11. Cost scoring calculation sequence for LATP.

Input	Amount	Unit	Unit price (€/kg)	I_{cost}
Aluminium oxide	0.04	kg	23.60	0.94
Lithium carbonate	0.13	kg	154.60	19.33
Ammonium dihydrogen phosphate	0.90	kg	14.88	13.35
Titanium dioxide	0.35	kg	35.20	12.43
			TOTAL	46.04

Finally, **Table 12** shows the normalized scores of the rest of the assessed cathode coatings. As observed, LATP clearly presents the lowest production cost compared to lithium zirconate and lithium borate. The calculation process for the rest of materials evaluated in this deliverable follows an analogous approach.

Table 12. Cost scoring calculation sequence for LATP.

MATERIAL	I_{cost}	NORMALISED SCORE
LATP	46.04	0.12
Li_2ZrO_3	199.65	0.53
Li_3BO_3	374.34	1.00

4.5. LCA SINGLE SCORE

The **LCA single score** is a comprehensive indicator employed to consolidate multiple environmental impacts into a single, weighted value, which facilitates a more direct comparison between materials or processes.

Weighting plays a critical role in this process, as it involves multiplying the normalised results of each impact categories by a weighting factor that reflects the relative importance of that category. As outlined by Sala et al. [15], the weighted results are expressed in the same unit (millipoint – mPt –, which is dimensionless), making them comparable and additive.

However, **weighting introduces a value judgement** to the LCA results, as the choice of weighting factors can significantly influence the score and, consequently, the conclusions drawn from the LCA. For this reason, weighting is often viewed as a controversial step in the LCA process [36]. In the context of deliverable, the LCA single score serves as one of the key parameters in the scoring system, complementing the other three (hazard, criticality, and cost) and thus enabling a holistic comparison of the proposed

materials in the SOLVE project. **Table 13** presents the normalized LCA single score for the three cathode coating categories.

Table 13. Cathode coating LCA single scores and normalized scores.

MATERIAL	LCA SINGLE SCORE	NORMALISED SCORE
LATP	2.38	0.71
Li ₂ ZrO ₃	0.93	0.28
Li ₃ BO ₃	3.35	1.00

As shown in **Table 13**, the normalized LCA single scores highlight differences in the overall environmental performance of the three cathode coating materials. When looking at the aggregated single score across all impact categories, **lithium zirconate** appears as the option with the lowest burden, while **lithium borate** shows the highest, and **LATP** lies in between.

However, it is important to note that the interpretation depends strongly on the scope of the assessment. In **Figure 10**, LATP was identified as the most sustainable option based on the subset of impact categories prioritised within the streamlined LCA carried out in this deliverable (i.e., those most relevant to battery manufacturing), where it consistently outperformed the alternatives. In contrast, when expanding the perspective to the full set of 16 impact categories used in the single score method, **lithium zirconate** achieves the lowest overall result.

In other words, LATP represents the best compromise within the impact categories directly aligned with SOLVE objectives, while lithium zirconate demonstrates stronger performance in a broader, more general sustainability context. As is the case here, analogous situations may also arise for other battery components.

4.6. SAFE AND SUSTAINABLE BY DESIGN (SSBD) SCORECARD

This section provides a **materials scorecard** that includes the normalised scores for each category assessed in the previous sections, following the scoring system methodology presented in *Section 2.2*.

Table 14 shows the SSbD scores for all evaluated materials across the four indicators – **hazard, criticality, cost, and environmental impact** – along with the **aggregated score**, which reflects the overall sustainability profile of each material alternative.

Table 14. Summary of the SSbD scores for all assessed materials.

SUBCOMPONENT	MATERIAL	HAZARD	CRITICALITY	COST	LCA SINGLE SCORE	AGGREGATED SCORE
CAM POWDER	Li-rich NMC	0.98	1.00	1.00	0.98	3.97
	NMC 85:5:10	1.00	0.68	0.34	1.00	3.03
CAM COATING	LATP	0.33	1.00	0.12	0.71	2.17
	Li ₂ ZrO ₃	0.54	0.05	0.53	0.28	1.40
	Li ₃ BO ₃	1.00	0.20	1.00	1.00	3.20
CONDUCTIVE ADDITIVES	Carbon black	1.00	0.00	4.23·10 ⁻³	0.02	1.02
	VGCF	0.79	0.00	1.00	1.00	2.79
	LiBOB	0.67	0.09	0.09	1.00	1.85
Li SALTS	LiTFSI	0.87	1.00	1.00	0.68	3.55
	LiFSI	1.00	0.83	0.96	0.39	3.17
PLASTICISER	PYR14TFSI	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	4.00

SUBCOMPONENT	MATERIAL	HAZARD	CRITICALITY	COST	LCA SINGLE SCORE	AGGREGATED SCORE
	PYR14FSI	0.93	0.48	0.52	0.60	2.58
HSPE CERAMIC FILLER	LATP	0.21	1.00	0.05	0.27	1.53
	Si@LATP	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	4.00
LiM ANODE BARRIER LAYER	LLZO	0.42	0.43	0.31	0.36	1.52
	Li ₃ N	1.00	0.43	1.00	1.00	3.43
	LIPON	0.84	1.00	0.57	0.45	2.86

Once the overall results are presented, the SSbD scorecards for each specific battery component are presented from **Figure 16** to **Figure 22**.

Figure 16: Materials scorecard for the assessed CAM powders.

Figure 16 presents the SSbD scores per mAh of theoretical capacity for the two assessed CAMs: Li-rich NMC and NMC 85:5:10. Although they are not competing alternatives (as already discussed), this comparison provided insights into their relative sustainability. Looking at the general picture, it could be stated that **NMC 85:5:10** slightly outperforms Li-rich NMC overall. Both materials present similar hazard and LCA scores, but the main differences lie in their criticality and cost, where NMC 85:5:10 shows lower values, reaching 68% and 34% of those of Li-rich NMC, respectively.

Figure 17 shows the scorecard for the assessed **CAM coating** materials. Among them, **lithium zirconate** stands out as the most sustainable option, presenting the lowest criticality (0.05) and LCA single score (0.28). **LATP** shows intermediate results, but is highly penalised by its high criticality, linked to the presence of several CRMs within its composition (Li, Al, and P). By contrast, it presents the lowest cost score among the three options. Finally, **lithium borate** shows the highest scores for hazard, cost, and environmental impact, clearly indicating that it is the least sustainable option among the evaluated coatings.

Figure 17: Materials scorecard for the assessed cathode active material coatings.

Figure 18: Materials scorecard for the assessed cathode conductive additives.

Following with the conductive additives for the catholyte, **Figure 18** compares the SSbD scores of carbon black and vapor-grown carbon-fibres (VGCF). It can be seen that **both materials show a criticality score of zero**, since they do not rely on CRMs during their synthesis. However, **VGCF exhibits significantly higher cost and environmental impact scores** due to its energy- and resource-intensive synthesis process compared to that from carbon black, making the latter the most balanced option in terms of sustainability. Nevertheless, the higher NFPA flammability rating of carbon black indicates a greater handling risk, which should also be carefully considered in the material selection process.

Figure 19: Materials scorecard for the assessed cathode lithium salts.

Figure 19 compares the SSbD of the three proposed lithium salts: LiBOB, LiTFSI, and LiFSI. Among them, **LiBOB** clearly stands out as the most sustainable option overall, showing a significant low criticality and cost scores in comparison to LiTFSI and LiFSI. This advantage is mainly attributed to its simpler synthesis route and the absence of fluorinated compounds, which are present in both LiTFSI and LiFSI, increasing their criticality and production costs. Moreover, LiBOB is the least hazardous option, but on the other hand, it carries the highest environmental burdens among the three assessed options.

Among the fluorinated Li-salts, no major differences are observed. Although LiFSI slightly outperforms LiTFSI in terms of environmental and criticality aspects, LiBOB remains the most favorable candidate from a sustainability perspective, provided its electrochemical performance meets the application requirements.

Figure 20. Materials scorecard for the assessed cathode plasticisers.

Figure 20 presents the materials scorecard for the two proposed plasticisers: PYR14TFSI and PYR14FSI. The results clearly show that **PYR14FSI** should be the most preferable option in terms of sustainability. While both ionic liquids exhibit similar hazard scores, PYR14FSI presents the **lowest score in each one of the indicators**, with a special mention to its criticality and cost, which are half of those from PYR14TFSI.

This difference stems from anion present in each formulation. The TFSI anion contains a higher quantity of fluorinated components that increase the environmental footprint, criticality, and production costs of PYR14TFSI.

Figure 21 compares the SSbD scores of the two ceramic fillers considered for the HSPE: LAMP and its silane-modified version, Si@LAMP. The results show that **LAMP** logically performs substantially better across all indicators except criticality, which remains identical for both materials, as they share the same base composition and CRM content.

Figure 21: Materials scorecard for the assessed HSPE ceramic fillers.

The much higher aggregated score of Si@LAMP can be attributed to its more complex synthesis process. Since LAMP is used as a precursor, the Si@LAMP route inherently includes the full environmental and cost burden of LAMP production, plus additional inputs such as silane precursors, solvents, and washing agents. These extra reagents not only raise production costs but also increase the overall environmental footprint and hazard potential of the process.

Consequently, despite the potential performance enhancement provided by the silane coating, LAMP remains the more sustainable and less hazardous option under the current assessment boundaries.

Finally, **Figure 22** presents the materials scorecard of the three assessed barrier layers for the LiM anode. Among them, **LLZO** emerges as the best performer across all indicators. On the contrary, **lithium nitride** is the worst option in terms of hazard, cost, and LCA single score, mainly due to the use of lithium metal as feedstock. **LiPON** lies in between, offering improved environmental and cost performance compared to lithium nitride, but showing the highest criticality among the three options.

In summary, LLZO combines lower hazard potential, reduced criticality concerns, and a more favourable life-cycle profile, making it the most sustainable barrier layer material among those evaluated.

Figure 22: Materials scorecard for the assessed lithium metal anode barrier layers.

As a final remark, it should be noted that the aggregated results are **indicative**, as all indicators were assigned equal weight in this preliminary evaluation. This approach provides a transparent and balanced comparison among materials; however, it does not reflect potential prioritisation that may arise in real-world design or industrial contexts. Depending on the **specific goals or constraints of the developer**, such as safety prioritisation, cost-effectiveness, or supply chain resilience, greater weight could be assigned to one or more of these indicators to tailor the SSbD assessment to the application's needs.

5. SSB DESIGN FOR RECYCLABILITY

5.1. SCOPE AND MATERIALS

The scope of the recyclability study focuses on identifying the challenges posed by the development of a solid-state battery with a metal anode and the impact of the selected components on safety, emissions and performance. The study will lay the foundations for optimizing the recycling strategy during the project in line with the industrial battery recycling infrastructure in Europe. In addition, it sets the objective of complying with European Regulation 2023/1542, which targets are defined in **Table 15**.

Table 15. Recycling targets.

	31/12/2027	31/12/2031	31/12/2025	31/12/2030
<i>Average weight</i>	-	-	65%	70%
<i>Lithium</i>	50%	80%	-	-
<i>Cobalt, nickel</i>	90%	95%	-	-
<i>Copper</i>	90%	95%	-	-

For lithium related batteries the average weight to be recovered is defined as 65 and 70% for 2025 and 2030, respectively. While the critical and strategical raw materials from the cathode and the current collectors are defined at a recovery rate of 90 and 95% for 2027 and 2031, respectively. Lithium, on the other hand, showed less ambitious targets at 50 and 80% for 2027 and 2031, respectively.

The development of an all-solid-state battery involves significant changes in the formulation and selection of the components to be used compared to those established in commercial products with liquid electrolytes. A pre-selection of these elements which are used for the development of the SOLVE battery are shown in **Table 16**. For the cathode compartment, the main difference lies in the use of inactive materials, such as polymers and plasticisers. While in conventional batteries this consists mainly of PVDF, in this case a larger amount of polymer must be incorporated along with plasticisers to achieve performance in line with the parameters defined in deliverable D.1.1. A similar behaviour is observed for the electrolyte, where the most common solvents (EC, DEC, EMC) are replaced by PVDF, plasticisers, and ceramic material. The electrolyte used in commercial cells (LiPF₆) is substituted with components compatible with solid-state development. These components, such as LiTFSI, PYR14TFSI, etc. include high-fluorinated organic compounds which are considered as PFAS according to ECHA definitions [37] now being adopted (-CF₃, highly persistent bond).

Finally, in the anode compartment, the presence of metallic lithium replaces graphite, thus increasing the safety challenges in the recycling process. The rest of the components, such as current collectors (Cu and Al) and cathode material (NMC), remain similar to those used in existing batteries and do not present major technical or safety challenges in terms of recycling. At first glance, the selection of the components brings relevant challenges to the EoL management in terms of safety and further downstream activities. Nevertheless, as further discussed, the design of tailored recycling strategy will properly tackle the issues, and it will be demonstrated in the upcoming activities.

Table 16. Summary of the pre-selected components.

Component	Normalization factor
Cathode	
Current collector	Carbon coated Al foil
CAM	$\text{LiNi}_{0.85}\text{Mn}_{0.05}\text{Co}_{0.10}\text{O}_2$
CAM coatings	Li_3BO_3 Li_2ZrO_3 $\text{Li}_{1.3}\text{Al}_{0.3}\text{Ti}_{1.7}(\text{PO}_4)_3$
Conductive additives	C45 C65 VGCF
Polymers	PVDF PVDF-HFP HSV
Li salts	LITFSI LiFSI LiBOB
Plasticisers	PYR14TFSI PYR14FSI PYR13TFSI
Solid polymer electrolyte	
Polymer	PVDF-HFP
Li salts	LITFSI LiFSI LiBOB
Plasticisers	PYR14TFSI PYR14FSI
Ceramic fillers	$\text{Li}_{1.3}\text{Al}_{0.3}\text{Ti}_{1.7}(\text{PO}_4)_3$ (LATP) $\text{Li}_{1.2}\text{Al}_{0.2}\text{Si}_{0.2}\text{Ti}_{1.6}(\text{PO}_4)_3$ (LATP)
Anode	
Current collector	Cu foil
Li metal deposition configuration	R2R-PLD Li / Cu (CC) / R2R-PLD Li
Alloying elements	Mg (by PLD) In (by PLD)
Barrier layers	a-C (PLD on Li metal) Li3N LLZO (PLD on Li metal)

5.2. CONVENTIONAL RECYCLING PROCESSES

To evaluate the recyclability of the newly developed Battery of the SOLVE project a study of the state-of-the-art recycling technology was performed. Based on the use case of the batteries, different pretreatments are necessary to make the input stream useable for the recycling.

Battery pack systems:

Modules or cell-to-pack designs have varying formats and use different production designs. Therefore, a very heterogeneous input can be found, and manual dismantling is used as a standard operation. Not all the packs can be fully discharged before dismantling to module or cell level. In this case, the discharge is shifted after the dismantling. In this case safety aspects need to be addressed carefully to protect the staff.

Batteries derived from small applications have an even larger chemical distribution of cells used in different applications but do not need a complicated dismantling procedure. However, different downstream processes require well sorted battery streams. This sorting is mainly done by trained labour indicating the cell chemistries by different optical markers and geometries. To review the required quality from the downstream process, a study of the recycling strategies is done.

Prior to the cell recycling, additional steps can be applied for increasing the recycling rate of full battery systems from different applications. Especially, batteries received from stationary storage solutions or transportation applications contain extensive periphery, that could significantly affect the purity of the obtained fractions. These elements can be removed through individual dismantling protocols designed for each storage solution. The extracted components are shown in **Figure 23**. As it can be appreciated, roughly 40% of the battery packs relate to passive material. Which can be dismantled and recycled according to individual and already existing recycling technologies.

MATERIAL COMPOSITION OF EV-PACKS

Figure 23: Material composition of NMC battery packs. Data modified from [38].

To ensure the safe and efficient handling of lithium-ion batteries (LIBs) during recycling, it is often necessary to fully discharge the cells prior to mechanical or chemical processing. This step mitigates the risk of thermal runaway, short circuits, or accidental energy release during dismantling, being a severe hazard to the staff. Discharging protocols can be broadly categorized into electrical and chemical methods, each offering distinct operational benefits and limitations depending on the battery type, format, and intended downstream process.

Electrical discharging involves connecting the battery to a controlled resistive load or energy recovery system, allowing the stored energy to be safely dissipated or redirected. In advanced setups, this energy can be fed back into the power grid, offering a sustainable and economically attractive option. This method is particularly suitable for large-format battery packs with uniform cell chemistries and configurations, such as those found in electric vehicles or stationary storage systems [39].

Chemical discharging, on the other hand, typically utilizes an electrolytic saltwater bath to induce a controlled electrochemical reaction that neutralizes the battery's charge. This approach is advantageous for mixed battery streams, as it can accommodate various cell chemistries and physical formats simultaneously. Moreover, it offers scalability and cost-efficiency, making it well-suited for industrial applications where battery heterogeneity is common [40]. The disadvantage of this method is that it produces considerable amounts of process water, which must be treated afterwards. Cross-contamination can also occur and must be considered. Additionally, the discharging time is significantly higher compared to electrical discharging (24 h compared to 1-5 h) [39,41].

Selecting the appropriate discharging method requires careful consideration of the battery's design, residual energy content, and the safety requirements of the recycling process. The experience of handling high amounts of SSBs in recycling facilities is very limited, mainly, due to the low market share. Critical hazards need to be addressed as these batteries can contain metallic lithium, and the amount can be reduced to a minimum by an individual discharging protocol. However, the contact of water and humidity with the inner cell needs to be avoided, as the reactivity is considerably high.

The goal is to recover as many materials used in batteries as possible from these in **Table 16** available components. To fulfil this task, three different recycling strategies are currently available on the market. Pyrometallurgy, hydrometallurgy and direct recycling opportunities. Each of the routes can produce different products in varying qualities, further explained in **Table 17**.

Table 17. Processes and steps in most prominent LIB recycling approaches. Adapted figure from [42].

Pyrometallurgy

This process enables a high available recycling capacity as the robustness and varying inactive components do not affect the efficiency. Additionally, its adaption to shifting cell chemistries is fast due to the versatility, simplicity and no need for Battery preparation. The batteries are directly introduced to the smelting oven. The remaining energy and the combustion of organic material provides the required energy and temperature. Harsh thermal conditions are used to smelt the complete battery at ca. 1500 °C. Lithium, aluminium and polymers are lost in the slag and commonly not recovered. High energy consumption during the smelting and the need for further processing for elemental separation contribute most to the operation [43], [44].

Hydrometallurgy

Hydrometallurgy is a promising method for recycling LIBs due to its ability to dissolve metals in water-based acidic or alkaline solutions. It stands out for being cost-effective, requiring low energy (with operating temperatures below 100 °C) [44], and having a relatively small environmental impact. However, the process is technically complex and generates significant amounts of wastewater, thus increasing the chemical consumption.

The technique focuses on recovering valuable metals such as lithium, cobalt, nickel, and manganese from spent LIBs. It consists of two main steps: first, leaching, where metals are dissolved into a solution; followed

by a recovery, where these metals are extracted from the solution and converted into usable forms like pure metals, cathode materials, or precursors [44].

During leaching, valuable elements are transformed into metal ions, while impurities like aluminium and iron, as well as non-dissolved solids such as graphite, are removed individually. The leaching process can be carried out using acidic or alkaline leachates, depending on factors like recovery efficiency, purification costs, and environmental impact. Commonly used acids are nitric, chloric, sulfuric acid or organic acids like citric malic or oxalic acid to dissolve the metals to form the salt. Because of the low leaching efficiencies in most of the processes the addition of hydrogen peroxide is needed to increase the dissolution efficiency.

After leaching, further refining steps such as precipitation, solvent extraction, ion exchange, or electrolysis are used to isolate and purify the recovered metals.

Further improvements are reported by academia from the bioleaching where bacteria are extracting target metals individual from an aqueous suspension of black mass in water. This approach can reduce the usage chemicals and elevated temperatures. However, this approach is not yet installed to treat larger amounts exceeding laboratory or pilot scale level.

Direct recycling

Direct recycling is an emerging and highly promising method for recovering materials from spent lithium-ion batteries by preserving and reusing the functional components-especially cathode materials-without breaking them down into individual elements. Unlike pyrometallurgical or hydrometallurgical processes, which involve high temperatures or chemical dissolution, direct recycling aims to retain the structure and performance of battery materials, making it both energy-efficient and potentially more sustainable [44].

The process typically begins with mechanical disassembly, where batteries are safely discharged, opened, and separated into components such as casings, current collectors, and active materials. The focus then shifts to the recovery and reconditioning of cathode materials, which are cleaned, re-lithiated, and thermally treated to restore their electrochemical properties. This allows the materials to be reused in new batteries with minimal loss in performance [45].

One of the key advantages of direct recycling is its low energy consumption and reduced chemical usage, which translates into a smaller environmental footprint. Additionally, it enables the preservation of material value, especially for complex cathode chemistries like NMC (Lithium Nickel-Manganese-Cobalt Oxide) or LFP (Lithium Iron Phosphate), which are difficult to separate and purify through conventional methods [45].

However, direct recycling faces several challenges. The process requires precise sorting of battery types and chemistries, as mixed materials can compromise the quality of the recycled product. It demands advanced technologies for material reconditioning and standardization across battery designs to make large-scale implementation feasible.

Recent developments in the recycling industry emphasize pyrometallurgical and hydrometallurgical approaches for the recovery of critical raw materials, as illustrated in **Figure 24**. The data reveal a clear upward trend in research activity related to battery recycling, reflecting a growing industrial and academic interest in this domain. While both pyrometallurgical and hydrometallurgical methods demonstrate comparable publication volumes, hydrometallurgy exhibits a modest increasing prominence in the field. However, the volume for direct recycling approaches is ten times less than other investigated ones.

Figure 24: Publication trend of the major recycling methods direct recycling, pyrometallurgy and hydrometallurgical treatment in the years 2020 and 2023. Data modified from [42].

5.3. PERFORMANCE EVALUATION AND MATERIAL FLOW ANALYSIS

The main challenge for the recycling of the SOLVE battery is to properly separate the fractions targeting efficient treatments for the recovery of materials. The de-activation process is essential to ensure a safe processing of batteries which, as already mentioned, can be done mainly through mechanical or thermal processes. Thermal deactivation is preferred over state-of-the-art (SoA) processes such as direct lithium-metal recovery (e.g., Blue Solutions [46]) because the performance of the SOLVE solid-state battery in these methods remains uncertain. Existing SoA processes are primarily designed for polymer-based solid-state batteries without ceramic fillers, whereas SOLVE incorporates ceramic components that may behave differently under such conditions. In contrast, thermal processing offers a robust and universal approach by effectively neutralizing reactive metallic lithium and simultaneously decomposing organic compounds and PFAS, thereby mitigating environmental and safety risks while preparing cleaner material streams for subsequent recovery steps.

Table 18: Deactivation of LIBs and SOLVE-SSB.

		Mechanical		Thermal	
		LIBs	SSB	LIBs	SSB
Safety	Ignition	Green	Red	Green	Yellow
	Hazardous comp.	Green	Green	Green	Green
Technical	Energy	Green	Green	Green	Green
	Chemicals	Green	Yellow	Green	Green
	Emissions	Green	Green	Green	Green
Performance	Purity	Green	Red	Green	Green
	Yields	Green	Red	Green	Green
	Fractions	Green	Red	Green	Green

The evaluation performed in **Table 18** indicates several aspects of the recycling process that has been taken into account to define a recycling strategy and ensure the sustainability of the SOLVE battery based on the selected components (**Table 17**). The table shows a comparison between the conventional batteries (LIBs) and the SSB for the main pre-treatment from the recycler perspective. The safety aspects were evaluated in terms of ignition and potential human hazard. During the mechanical pre-treatment the batteries are crushed, and the volatile organic solvent is released, which in case of shortcut resulting from residual energy stored in the battery could lead to ignition. To overcome the issue all the batteries must be deep discharged before proceeding to the treatment. Within the thermal pre-treatment the batteries are processed inside the oven under inert atmosphere, therefore the state of charge prior the treatment must not be controlled. In both processes the off gas is properly collected and treated to avoid hazardous emissions. In terms of safety,

the most concerning hazardous components selected for the SOLVE battery (**Table 19**) are the anode, as metallic lithium, and the fluorinated compounds used as polymer, salts and plasticiser which require proper remediation. The production of black mass through the mechanical route might lead to presence of lithium metallic in the obtained fractions, thus requiring operating under dry atmosphere in further recycling steps. At the same time the fluorinated compounds will remain in the recovered fraction (polymer, active material powders, current collectors, etc.) as impurities.

On the other hand, the thermal processing can de-activate the metallic lithium while degrading the fluorinated compounds. The thermal stability of PVDF and lithium salts such as LiTFSI [47], LiFSI [48] and LiBOB [49] show a significant mass reduction from in the range of 300 until 600 °C. During the thermal processing the hazardous compounds are degraded and collected in the off gas, hence reducing the fluorinated organic content in the fractions.

Table 19. GHS symbols and H-Statement for lithium salts.

LiTFSI		H301 – H314 – H373 – H412
LiFSI		H302 – H315 – H318 – H316fd
LiBOB		H315 – H319 – H355

In terms of energy and chemical consumption the impact of the SOLVE battery is expected to be like the state of the art. However, for the mechanical processing the atmosphere must not only be inert to avoid ignition but also dry. The thermal behaviour of the SOLVE battery will be evaluated during the recycling optimization. Finally, the emissions from the pyrolysis chamber are expected to be higher in terms of hydrogen fluoride, because of the larger number of fluorinated compounds. Nevertheless, the off-gas treatment will be properly adapted to ensure a complete capture of hazardous emissions. The emissions in terms of CO₂ are higher when comparing the pre-treatment alone. However, when considering the overall processing including the metal extraction the emissions are balanced 2.2 and 2.3 of kg CO₂eq/kg module equivalent [52] for thermal-hydro and mechanical-hydro combination, respectively.

Finally, the most important points of the evaluation were identified in the performance. The use of polymer material and plasticiser engage both the recovery and the purity of the obtained fractions when operating through mechanical pre-treatment, since the black mass is bonded to the polymer fraction. The efficiency of the delamination process to liberate the active material it is directly affected as well as the further sieving. On the other hand, the collected streams could not be processed through existing downstream processes since the cross-contamination bring compounds in the recovered fractions that cannot be processed. In contrast, the thermal pre-treatment decomposes the polymer and plasticisers degrading the structure and releasing the active material, thus increasing the recovery rate, purity and the overall recycling efficiency.

Considering the previous evaluation based on the components selected for the SOLVE battery, the recycling strategy contemplates a previous sorting step from the conventional batteries to be processed in separated streams.

Nevertheless, the technology and infrastructure can be adapted from existing processes by following the procedure shown in **Figure 25**. The highlighted strategy does not also tackle the safety issues derived from the metallic lithium on the anode but also enables its conversion to soluble salts. Additionally, the removal of PFAS and fluorinated organic compounds along with the polymer and organic compounds guarantees no further environmental threat to the further processing steps and contributes to reduce the related costs such as wastewater processing.

The discharging process ensures a decrease of the lithium content in metallic form, although the guarantee of a complete depletion is not

Figure 25: Suggested recycling strategy for the SOLVE's battery.

The conversion of lithium metal towards soluble salts enables its extraction and recovery as lithium carbonate through a water-based process, thus producing a delithiated black mass suitable for the hydrometallurgical processing and the recovery of nickel and cobalt

6. CONCLUSIONS

The successful implementation of the streamlined Life Cycle Assessment (LCA) and the Safe and Sustainable by Design scoring framework in this deliverable established a robust, quantitative basis for making eco-design decisions during the early development of novel SSB components. The results consistently demonstrated that selecting sustainable materials often involves navigating complex trade-offs, which the holistic SSbD scorecard, based on the equally weighted aggregation of hazard, criticality, cost, and environmental impact, helped to clarify.

Regarding the two CAM powders, the assessment showed that **NMC 85:5:10** slightly outperformed Li-rich NMC in the aggregated score, driven by lower criticality and cost. However, for both chemistries, the LCA revealed that the environmental impact is overwhelmingly attributable to the upstream supply chain of metal precursors, particularly **cobalt** and **nickel salts**. This finding emphasizes the critical importance of advancing recycling processes to recover these metals and mitigate the burdens associated with their primary extraction.

The analysis of **cathode coatings** identified lithium zirconate (Li_2ZrO_3) as the best environmental performer across the full suite of 16 LCA categories integrated into the single score, resulting in the lowest overall SSbD score. While lithium aluminium titanium phosphate (LATP) presented the lowest production cost, its score was significantly penalised by its high criticality index, stemming from the presence of multiple Critical Raw Materials (CRMs) like lithium, aluminium, and phosphate rock. Conversely, lithium borate (Li_3BO_3) consistently showed the highest scores for hazard, cost, and environmental impact, marking it as the least sustainable option.

In terms of **conductive additives**, **carbon black** proved to be the more sustainable and balanced choice, as both carbon black and Vapor Grown Carbon Fibers (VGCF) showed zero criticality. VGCF, however, carried significantly higher environmental impacts and costs, largely because its production process is extremely energy-intensive, with electricity consumption contributing 65-72% of its total impacts. A trade-off to consider is that carbon black possesses a higher NFPA flammability rating, indicating a greater handling risk.

For the **lithium salts**, **LiBOB** was determined to be the most favourable candidate overall due to its substantially lower cost and criticality compared to LiTFSI and LiFSI. This is due to its simpler synthesis route and the avoidance of fluorinated compounds, which increase the cost and criticality of the other options. While LiBOB did carry the highest LCA environmental burden among the three, LiTFSI was penalised by the use of methylchloride, a high-impact feedstock contributing significantly to non-cancerous human toxicity. For **plasticisers**, **PYR14FSI** was superior to PYR14TFSI across all SSbD indicators, with its criticality and cost being approximately half, a difference attributed to the lower burden of the FSI anion compared to the TFSI anion.

The complexity of the synthesis route proved detrimental for the **HSPE ceramic filler** comparison. Unmodified **LATP** consistently outperformed the silane-modified alternative, Si@LATP, because the Si@LATP synthesis requires additional processing steps involving large amounts of solvents, like ethanol and the APTMS silane precursor, significantly increasing its environmental, cost, and hazard burdens. Finally, the **LLZO** (Lithium lanthanum zirconium oxide) material was identified as the optimal **LiM anode barrier layer**, showcasing the best performance across all four SSbD indicators. This contrasts sharply with lithium nitride (Li_3N) which was the least sustainable, primarily due to the high environmental and cost burdens inherited from using lithium metal as feedstock.

In summary, the SSbD scorecard delivered specific, actionable eco-design recommendations for material selection, although it must be noted that these results are currently indicative as all four indicators were assigned equal weight in this preliminary evaluation. The final comprehensive assessment of the SSB technology, which will provide a full cradle-to-grave picture, including components currently excluded due to confidentiality or lack of industrial data (such as specific polymers and full anode configurations), will be

completed in Deliverable D4.4 once the component selections are finalized and validated at the prototype level.

The recyclability assessment of the SOLVE solid-state battery (SSB) highlighted significant safety and environmental concerns primarily associated with the use of metallic lithium as the anode material and the presence of fluorinated organic compounds, including PFAS (per- and polyfluoroalkyl substances). These components pose challenges due to their chemical reactivity, potential toxicity, and persistence in the environment. To address these issues, the selection of an appropriate pre-treatment process for battery deactivation is critical. This step ensures safe handling and facilitates the production of two key outputs: black mass, which contains valuable active materials, and base metal fractions, which can be recovered and reused individually.

Among the possible approaches, thermal deactivation has been pre-selected as the most promising strategy to be further optimized in a subsequent work package (WP). This technique offers a controlled way to neutralize reactive components, thereby minimizing hazards and improving material recovery of downstream processes. The optimized thermal route is expected to significantly reduce the consumption of chemical reagents during lithium extraction, which not only lowers environmental impact but also improves process economics. Furthermore, this method will generate a cleaner input stream for the recovery of critical metals such as nickel (Ni), cobalt (Co), and manganese (Mn), which are essential for battery manufacturing. In addition, PFAS are deactivated and the likelihood of enrichment of these chemicals in the environment is prevented.

The overall strategy of the project has been designed to align with and meet the stringent requirements set forth in the new EU Battery Regulation (EU 2023/1542), which emphasizes sustainability, resource efficiency, and safe recycling practices across the battery value chain.

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ANNEXES

A1. NFPA HAZARD CLASSIFICATION FOR THE DIFFERENT PRECURSORS

SUBSTANCE	FORMULA	HAZARD LEVEL			AGGREGATED RATING
		Health	Flammability	Instability	
Lithium hydroxide	LiOH	3	0	0	3
Nickel sulfate	NiSO ₄	2	0	0	2
Manganese sulfate	MnSO ₄	1	0	0	1
Cobalt sulfate	CoSO ₄	2	0	0	2
Sodium hydroxide	NaOH	3	0	1	4
Ammonium hydroxide	NH ₄ OH	3	1	0	4
Lithium nitrate	LiNO ₃	2	0	2	4
Nickel nitrate	Ni(NO ₃) ₂	2	1	0	3
Cobalt nitrate	Co(NO ₃) ₂	3	1	1	5
Manganese nitrate	Mn(NO ₃) ₂	2	0	1	3
Urea	CH ₄ N ₂ O	1	0	0	1
Glycine	C ₂ H ₅ NO ₂	1	1	1	3
Aluminium oxide	Al ₂ O ₃	1	0	0	1
Lithium carbonate	Li ₂ CO ₃	1	0	0	1
Ammonium dihydrogen phosphate	(NH ₄) ₂ HPO ₄	1	0	0	1
Titanium dioxide	TiO ₂	1	0	0	1
Zirconium oxide	ZrO ₂	2	0	0	2
Boric acid	H ₃ BO ₃	2	0	1	3
Sulfur dioxide	SO ₂	3	0	0	3
Chlorine	Cl ₂	4	0	0	4
Methane	CH ₄	2	4	0	6
Hydrogen fluoride	HF	4	0	1	5
Silica	SiO ₂	0	0	0	0
Methylchloride	CH ₃ Cl	2	4	0	6
Ammonia	NH ₃	3	1	0	4
Sodium methoxide	CH ₃ ONa	3	3	2	8
Sulfuric acid	H ₂ SO ₄	3	0	2	5
Fluorosulfonic acid	HSO ₃ F	3	0	2	5
Lithium fluoride	LiF	2	0	0	2
Thionyl chloride	SOCl ₂	4	0	2	6
Urea	CH ₄ N ₂ O	1	0	0	1
Oxalic acid	C ₂ H ₂ O ₄	3	1	0	4
Lithium bis(trifluoromethanesulfonyl)imide	LiC ₂ F ₆ NO ₄ S ₂	3	1	0	4
1-methyl pyrrolidine	C ₅ H ₁₁ N	3	3	1	7

SUBSTANCE	FORMULA	HAZARD LEVEL			AGGREGATED RATING
		Health	Flammability	Instability	
Bromobutane	C ₄ H ₉ Br	1	3	0	4
Lithium bis(fluorosulfonyl)imide	LiF ₂ NO ₄ S ₂	3	0	0	3
Trichloroethylene	C ₂ HCl ₃	2	1	0	3
Ultrapure water	H ₂ O	0	0	0	0
Hydrogen	H ₂	0	4	0	4
Butene	C ₄ H ₈	1	4	0	5
Decarbonized water	H ₂ O	0	0	0	0
Sodium tetrahydridoborate	NaBH ₄	3	1	2	6
Acetic acid	CH ₃ COOH	3	2	0	5
Hydrogen sulfide	H ₂ S	4	4	0	8
Hexane	C ₆ H ₁₄	1	3	0	4
Ferrocene	Fe(C ₅ H ₅) ₂	2	2	0	4
Hydrochloric acid	HCl	3	0	0	3
Carbon black	C	0	2	0	2
(3-Aminopropyl)trimethoxysilane	C ₆ H ₁₇ NO ₃ Si	2	2	0	4
Ethanol	C ₂ H ₆ O	2	3	0	5
Lanthanum oxide	La ₂ O ₃	1	0	0	1
Lithium metal	Li	3	2	2	7
Nitrogen	N ₂	0	0	0	0
Lithium oxide	Li ₂ O	3	0	0	3
Phosphorus pentoxide	P ₂ O ₅	3	0	1	4
Ammonia	NH ₃	3	1	0	4
Phosphorus pentachloride	PCl ₅	3	0	2	5

A2. EF 3.1 NORMALISATION AND WEIGHTING FACTORS FOR THE CALCULATION LCA SINGLE SCORE

Impact category	Acronym	Normalisation factor	Weighting factor (%)
Acidification	AC	55.56954123	6.20%
Climate change	CC	7553.083163	21.06%
Ecotoxicity, freshwater	ETF	56716.58634	1.92%
Particulate matter	PM	0.000595	8.96%
Eutrophication, marine	E-AM	19.54518155	2.96%
Eutrophication, freshwater	E-AF	1.606852128	2.80%
Eutrophication, terrestrial	E-T	176.7549998	3.71%
Human toxicity, cancer	HT-C	0.0000173	2.13%
Human toxicity, non-cancer	HT-NC	0.000129	1.84%
Ionizing radiation	IR	4220.16339	5.01%
Land use	LU	819498.1829	7.94%
Ozone depletion	OD	0.052348383	6.31%

Impact category	Acronym	Normalisation factor	Weighting factor (%)
Photochemical ozone formation	POF	40.85919773	4.78%
Resource use, fossils	RU-F	65004.25966	8.32%
Resource use, minerals, and metals	RU-MM	0.063622615	7.55%
Water use	WU	11468.70864	8.51%

A3. LCIA RESULTS

CAM powder				
Impact category	Abbrev.	Unit	NMC 85:5:10	Li-rich NMC
Climate change	CC	kg CO ₂ eq.	8.71E-05	1.19E-04
Ecotoxicity - freshwater	ETF	CTUe	1.49E-03	2.14E-03
Human toxicity, cancer	HT-C	CTUh	4.18E-13	5.17E-13
Human toxicity, non-cancer	HT-NC	CTUh	4.72E-12	3.18E-12
Resource use, fossils	RU-F	MJ	1.40E-03	1.56E-03
Resource use, minerals and metals	RU-MM	kg Sb eq.	9.26E-09	5.90E-09
Water use	WU	m ³ depriv.	2.70E-04	2.46E-04

Coating CAM - Cathode					
Impact category	Abbrev.	Unit	LATP	Li ₂ ZrO ₃	Li ₃ BO ₃
Climate change	CC	kg CO ₂ eq.	4.37E+00	8.20E+00	1.60E+01
Ecotoxicity - freshwater	ETF	CTUe	5.59E+01	1.04E+02	2.65E+02
Human toxicity, cancer	HT-C	CTUh	8.42E-09	3.33E-08	4.88E-08
Human toxicity, non-cancer	HT-NC	CTUh	8.42E-08	1.18E-07	2.89E-07
Resource use, fossils	RU-F	MJ	5.17E+01	9.48E+01	1.80E+02
Resource use, minerals and metals	RU-MM	kg Sb eq.	8.75E-05	1.17E-04	1.52E-03
Water use	WU	m ³ depriv.	7.34E+00	6.65E+00	6.89E+00

Conductive additives - Cathode				
Impact category	Abbrev.	Unit	Carbon black	VGCF
Climate change	CC	kg CO ₂ eq.	2.40E+00	1.09E+02
Ecotoxicity - freshwater	ETF	CTUe	5.37E+00	5.37E+02
Human toxicity, cancer	HT-C	CTUh	5.68E-09	5.79E-07
Human toxicity, non-cancer	HT-NC	CTUh	9.61E-09	8.91E-07
Resource use, fossils	RU-F	MJ	7.89E+01	2.67E+03
Resource use, minerals and metals	RU-MM	kg Sb eq.	8.37E-06	4.69E-04
Water use	WU	m ³ depriv.	1.47E-01	4.59E+01

Lithium salts - Cathode					
Impact category	Abbrev.	Unit	LiBOB	LiTFSI	LiFSI
Climate change	CC	kg CO ₂ eq.	2.35E+01	3.83E+01	1.73E+01
Ecotoxicity - freshwater	ETF	CTUe	2.87E+02	3.76E+02	3.18E+02
Human toxicity, cancer	HT-C	CTUh	4.98E-07	5.80E-08	6.44E-08
Human toxicity, non-cancer	HT-NC	CTUh	2.01E-07	3.96E-07	2.58E-07
Resource use, fossils	RU-F	MJ	2.30E+02	4.64E+02	1.60E+02
Resource use, minerals and metals	RU-MM	kg Sb eq.	6.84E-04	8.08E-05	2.51E-04
Water use	WU	m ³ depriv.	6.37E+00	6.16E+00	7.67E+00

Plasticiser - Cathode				
Impact category	Abbrev.	Unit	PYR14TFSI	PYR14FSI
Climate change	CC	kg CO ₂ eq.	2.97E+01	1.47E+01
Ecotoxicity - freshwater	ETF	CTUe	2.94E+02	2.42E+02
Human toxicity, cancer	HT-C	CTUh	5.01E-08	5.26E-08
Human toxicity, non-cancer	HT-NC	CTUh	-5.92E-08	1.73E-07
Resource use, fossils	RU-F	MJ	3.74E+02	1.68E+02
Resource use, minerals and metals	RU-MM	kg Sb eq.	5.80E-05	1.58E-04
Water use	WU	m ³ depriv.	6.67E+00	7.94E+00

Ceramic filler - HSPE				
Impact category	Abbrev.	Unit	LATP	Si@LATP
Climate change	CC	kg CO ₂ eq.	4.37E+00	8.43E+01
Ecotoxicity - freshwater	ETF	CTUe	5.59E+01	6.08E+02
Human toxicity, cancer	HT-C	CTUh	8.42E-09	2.93E-07
Human toxicity, non-cancer	HT-NC	CTUh	8.42E-08	4.81E-07
Resource use, fossils	RU-F	MJ	5.17E+01	1.11E+03
Resource use, minerals and metals	RU-MM	kg Sb eq.	8.75E-05	4.34E-04
Water use	WU	m ³ depriv.	7.34E+00	2.42E+01